

Book of Abstracts

4TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE – CURRENT STATE AND PERSPECTIVES

19-21 JUNE 2025.
NOVI SAD, SERBIA

ISBN: 978-86-7520-634-7

4th Antimicrobial Resistance - Current State and Perspectives 2025.

Book of Abstracts

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture
21000 Novi Sad, Trg D. Obradovića 8
Tel.:++(021) 6350711; 4853-308;
polj.uns.ac.rs

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Dear colleagues,

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to the 4th International Conference “Antimicrobial Resistance – current state and perspective”, held in Novi Sad, Serbia. This conference has grown into a dynamic and respected platform for sharing knowledge, fostering dialogue, and building interdisciplinary cooperation in tackling antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

This year’s program brings together near 90 speakers, researchers, and experts from across Europe and beyond, reflecting the diversity and complexity of AMR challenges. Through sessions and workshops, we address AMR from various perspectives including veterinary, medical, pharmaceutical, agricultural, food safety and environmental sciences, all within the integrated One Health framework. Beside, by encouraging dialogue between researchers, clinicians, policymakers, and industry representatives, this scientific meeting contributes to building evidence-based strategies to address AMR at multiple levels.

Topics such as antimicrobial stewardship in animal and human health, AMR monitoring and surveillance in human medicine, livestock, aquaculture and companion animals and regulatory frameworks such as WHO AWaRe classification demonstrate the urgency of collective and coordinated action. Special attention is given to the importance of monitoring antimicrobial consumption in both human and veterinary medicine. This integrated approach provides crucial insights for understanding usage trends, identifying potential risks, and optimizing interventions. Within the veterinary sector, this is exemplified by the presentation and discussion of the European Sales and Use of Antimicrobials for Veterinary Medicine reports, known as ESUAvet.

Important insights are offered into the role of biosecurity measures in reducing antibiotic dependence, along with the potential of probiotics and phytotherapeutics as alternative strategies in infection control. Considerable attention has also been given to the interpretation of antibiograms and the promotion of responsible prescribing practices, as well as to the growing concern of resistant zoonotic bacteria, biofilm-forming foodborne pathogens, and environmental spread of AMR. Contributions also explore emerging areas such as antifungal resistance in plant protection, circular economy practices to mitigate AMR spread, and the importance of monitoring residues of veterinary medicinal products in food of animal origin.

Antimicrobials remain indispensable, but their misuse continues to jeopardize their effectiveness. By promoting responsible use, surveillance, innovation, and cross-sector collaboration, we can preserve their efficacy and protect global health.

We thank you for your active participation and dedication to this mission. Let this conference inspire impactful dialogue, lasting collaborations, and forward-thinking strategies.

*dr Zorana Kovačević, associate professor
President of the scientific and program committee*

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FROM AMR ONE HEALTH MAPPING TOWARDS HARMONIZED SURVEILLANCE SYSTEMS

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) remains one of the most challenging veterinary public health issues of recent decades, with consequences that span human, animal, and environmental health. As the One Health approach has become central to understanding and combating the spread of AMR, various initiatives have sought to overcome the limitations of the traditional “silo” approach in research, planning, data collection, analysis, risk assessment, and risk management. The presentation will explore the evolution from fragmented data collection to more harmonized surveillance systems, using Latvia’s experience as a lens within the broader EU context. It will highlight progress in One Health AMR mapping across sectors in Latvia—tracing how integration of human, veterinary, and environmental data has developed within the framework of AMR surveillance and policy-making. Key challenges will also be addressed, including data interoperability, cross-sectoral governance, and resource disparities. Practical insights and lessons learned from Latvia’s “journey” will be shared, showcasing how targeted investments, stakeholder engagement, and regional collaboration can support the gradual development of cohesive and interoperable AMR surveillance systems. However, significant steps are still needed to achieve a truly comprehensive and harmonized approach to AMR surveillance and the implementation of a dynamic, regularly updated national AMR action plan.

Key words: Antimicrobial resistance, One Health, surveillance systems, data harmonization, cross-sectoral collaboration, public health policy, national AMR strategy

RESPONSIBLE USE OF ANTIMICROBIALS IN ANIMALS THROUGH ONE HEALTH PERSPECTIVE

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The global rise in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents a serious and growing threat to public health, posing a critical challenge that transcends human, animal, and environmental health. The One Health concept offers a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing this problem by acknowledging the close interconnection between people, animals, plants, and their shared environment. Animals, including companion animals, livestock, and wildlife, are recognized as important reservoirs and potential sources of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria and resistance genes that can spread across species and ecosystems. One of the fundamental components of the One Health approach is the promotion of antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) in all sectors, including veterinary medicine. Responsible use of antimicrobials in animals involves reducing unnecessary exposure, ensuring that treatments are based on accurate diagnosis, and applying appropriate antimicrobials in terms of spectrum, dosage, and duration. This also includes enhancing preventive measures such as vaccination, improved hygiene, better animal husbandry practices, and strengthened biosecurity on farms, which together reduce the need for antimicrobial use. Improving diagnostic capabilities is essential for targeted and timely therapy, minimizing empirical treatments and inappropriate prescriptions. In addition to clinical measures, surveillance systems and data collection play a central role in guiding antimicrobial policies and AMS programs. The monitoring of antimicrobial consumption in animals, categorized by animal species and production system, is vital for assessing risks and guiding interventions. The European Medicines Agency supports this through standardized methodologies, while the annual European Sales and Use of Antimicrobials for Veterinary Medicine reports, known as ESUAvet, provides harmonized and comparable data across European Union and European Economic Area countries. These reports offer valuable insights into usage trends and enable benchmarking among countries, helping stakeholders evaluate the effectiveness of national and regional AMS strategies. Raising awareness and providing targeted education for veterinarians, farmers, animal health professionals, and decision-makers are key to changing behaviors and promoting responsible antimicrobial use. These efforts, aligned with the principles of the One Health approach, are essential in reducing AMR and preserving the efficacy of existing antimicrobials. The development of sustainable policies must be based on collaboration between public health authorities, veterinary services, environmental experts, and the agricultural sector. Combating AMR requires a long-term coordinated action at local, national and global levels. Integrating responsible antimicrobial use with prevention, surveillance, and policy support within the One Health framework is essential to ensuring animal welfare, food safety and public health protection.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial consumption, antimicrobial stewardship, One Health

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Contract no. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117].

DIETARY APPROACHES TO REDUCE THE PREVALENCE OF AMR COLIFORMS IN STARTER CHICKENS

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The broiler chick faces a number of challenges in its first week of life. It has no contact with its mother, and it hatches from its egg into a hatchery from where it will be transferred to a crate and transported, with thousands of other chicks, to the production unit. Here it will be placed in a large shed where it will need to find the feed and water that it needs, and develop a healthy and resilient microbiome in its gut that will enable it to digest and utilise its feed efficiently while resisting infection by pathogenic (and potentially AMR) bacteria such as Avian Pathogenic *E. coli* (APEC). Establishing a diverse, healthy and resilient gut microbiome is key, but in the absence of a mother hen (as a source of commensal and beneficial microorganisms) this may be delayed. The administration of prophylactic antibiotics to very young birds may make the situation even worse, by reducing the diversity and development of the microbiome. This can be ameliorated to some extent with the administration of probiotics derived from the excreta of mature chickens, or by exposure to excreta from older birds (as is the case if litter is reused between batches). A vulnerable ‘window’ around 8-10 days of age has been observed, when there is a rapid increase in the prevalence of AMR (and potentially pathogenic) coliforms that can be isolated from the caecum. This usually subsides as the bird gets older, but this leaves the birds open to challenge in the first few days of life by opportunistic infections when their immune response is still immature, and this proliferation is despite an absence of antibiotic use. We have investigated various dietary interventions to try and reduce this prevalence. Maize is a more digestible carbohydrate source for broiler birds compared with wheat, but wheat is the main cereal source (and forms the basis of the poultry diet) in northern Europe. However, it was observed that feeding birds wheat rather than maize increased the probability of isolating AMR coliforms from the caecum. This may be a consequence of the pattern of caecal fermentation of the cereal fibre. However, fibre seemed to be beneficial when we have investigated different protein sources. We have observed that coliforms isolated from the caeca of young chicks fed feeds with a higher fibre content (rapeseed meal and sunflower meal) were associated with less ampicillin resistance compared with coliforms isolated from chicks fed soyabean meal. Chickens are insectivores, and feeding an insect protein (extracted black soldier fly larvae meal) was also associated with a lower prevalence of AMR. However, the fibrous feeds (and the insect meal) were often associated with lower and less efficient growth by the bird. The challenge therefore remains of how to formulate a diet that supports efficient growth, while also avoiding the proliferation of AMR coliforms in the gut of very young birds.

Keywords: Chicken, Fibre, Protein, Soya, Insect

Acknowledgments: I would like to acknowledge the insight and work of my colleagues and students, notably Professor Martin Woodward, Dr Ah Ran Lee, Dr Maha Aldeig, Nazmul Huda and also Chris Andrews, Jasmine Laws, Alex Loram, Millie Richards and Jasmine Wong.

AWaRe CLASSIFICATION: A GLOBAL FRAMEWORK FOR ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARSHIP AND RESISTANCE MANAGEMENT

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A clear demand exists for simple tools to improve the quality of antibiotic prescribing globally. In April 2017, the Expert Committee on the Selection and Use of Essential Medicines recommended changes to the World Health Organization (WHO) lists for adults (EML) and children (EMLc). The panel identified empiric first- and second-choice treatments for several of the most common infections, focusing on the choice of antibiotics used in most countries of the world. The WHO expert commission proposed the categorization of antibiotics into Access, Watch and Reserve antibiotics - AWaRe classification. According to the WHO recommendations from 2024., it is considered that drugs of first choice, Access, should account for 70% of the total consumption of antibiotics at the country level, and Watch (25%) and Reserve drugs (5%) should account for a total of 30%. The AWaRe classification is available on the WHO website: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-MHP-HPS-EML-2023.04>. Access antibiotics are recommended as a first or second choice treatment options for common infections due to a narrow spectrum of activity, good safety profile, low resistance potential and budget cost. Watch antibiotics are recommended only as first choice options for patients with infections where the causative pathogens are more likely to be resistant to Access antibiotics and more severe clinical presentation of the disease. Reserve antibiotics are recommended only for treatment of infection caused by the multidrug-resistant strains. Reducing the inappropriate use of Watch antibiotics is a key to control antibiotic resistance. In addition, the Technical Advisory Group on AWaRe (TAG-AWaRe), an advisory group to the WHO on antimicrobial use and stewardship, was recently established. The TAG-AWaRe provides technical advice to WHO to further develop and implement the AWaRe system, including the classification, book and indicators and targets, as a global antimicrobial stewardship tool. Countries are encouraged to use the AWaRe classification as a basis for developing their guidelines and reducing the total level of inappropriate antibiotic prescribing. The application of AWaRe in the practice, as well as for evaluations and monitoring of use, can contribute to reducing antimicrobial resistance and costs for patients and health systems.

Key words: AWaRe classification, antimicrobial, antimicrobial resistance

AMR – A GLOBAL PROBLEM: IS SERBIA ALSO PART OF THIS STORY?

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a serious health issue and one of the top 10 global public health threats of the 21st century. AMR arises and spreads due to the uncontrolled and inappropriate use of antibiotics, not only in human medicine but also in veterinary practice, agriculture, and food production. Infections caused by multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria complicate the treatment of common infections, increase the risk of therapeutic failure, prolong hospital stays, lead to higher morbidity and mortality, and create a greater economic burden on healthcare systems. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of people worldwide develop infections caused by multidrug-resistant pathogens each year. Surveillance of antimicrobial resistance in Serbia is carried out in the National Reference Laboratory for AMR (NRL for AMR) which was appointed by the Ministry of Health in 2008 and is located at the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, and through participation in the CAESAR (Central Asian and European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Resistance) network. Our country has been a member of this network since 2013. Clinical antimicrobial susceptibility data for eight bacterial species (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp., *Salmonella* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis/faecium*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) were collected from 24 clinical laboratories included in the national AMR surveillance network, with an estimated total national population coverage of 78%. All of these laboratories used EUCAST guidelines for antimicrobial susceptibility testing. In 2023, a total of 3,419 primary isolates of invasive bacteria (from blood cultures and cerebrospinal fluid) were confirmed. The surveillance data revealed alarmingly high levels of resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* to third-generation cephalosporins (92.6%), carbapenems (67.4%), and colistin (38.1%). Although carbapenem resistance in *Escherichia coli* remained low (0.6%), its emergence is still a concern. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Acinetobacter* spp. showed carbapenem resistance rates of 48.8% and 96.3%, respectively, while colistin resistance in these species was relatively low (1.4% and 3.6%). Among Gram-positive bacteria, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) accounted for 23.8% of isolates, vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* (VRE) for 47.9%, and penicillin-resistant *Streptococcus pneumoniae* for 22.4%. According to the report of NRL for AMR, Serbia remains among the European countries with the highest percentage of resistant isolates. Our data correspond to the values of the countries of Southern and Eastern Europe. Solving the problem of AMR requires a multidisciplinary approach that includes strengthening surveillance and resistance control systems, implementing antimicrobial surveillance policy, improving microbiological diagnostics, and ensuring continuous education for healthcare professionals and patients.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance, CAESAR Network, invasive isolates, antibiotics

ANTIMICROBIAL CONSUMPTION IN MONTENEGRO FROM 2009 to 2024

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Measuring antibiotic consumption is essential for monitoring usage trends, identifying usage pattern, linking use to resistance, evaluating stewardship efforts, and informing national strategies to promote responsible antibiotic use and combat resistance. In Montenegro, the Institute for Medicines and Medical Devices (CInMED) has been conducting regular surveillance of antimicrobial consumption, providing valuable insights into prescribing behaviors and guiding healthcare decision-making. This study aims to analyze the national consumption of systemic antibacterials (ATC group J01) over a 16-year period, from 2009 to 2024, using standardized WHO methodology. Trends in antibiotic consumption are examined using defined daily doses (DDD) per 1,000 inhabitants per day as the standard measurement unit. From 2009 to 2024, antibiotic consumption initially increased, peaking in 2011 (38.1 DDD/1000/day), followed by a sharp decline in 2012. This decrease continued with a period of stable lower consumption until 2019, after which consumption increased again, reaching approximately 30.8 DDD/1000/day in 2024. Antibiotic consumption analysis by ATC group (2009–2024) revealed an overall decrease after 2011, most notably in penicillins (J01C). In the period after 2020, several groups—including macrolides (J01F), cephalosporins (J01D), and aminoglycosides (J01G) have shown renewed increases, reflecting shifts in prescribing patterns that could be linked to the COVID-19 pandemic. Over the past 16 years, antimicrobial consumption in Montenegro has experienced notable fluctuations, characterized by an initial decline and a subsequent recent increase. The persistently high usage of specific antibiotic classes, especially beta-lactams, highlights the urgent need to enhance antimicrobial stewardship and surveillance efforts to mitigate the threat of antibiotic resistance.

Key words: antibiotics, defined daily doses, Montenegro, COVID-19

FINDINGS OF CONTINUOUS MONITORING OF CONSUMPTION ANTIMICROBIAL DRUGS IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Continuous monitoring of antimicrobial drugs consumption is very important, since consumption is associated with antimicrobial resistance. Valid 2014-2023 total antimicrobial use data of Bosnia and Herzegovina were analysed according to the WHO (World Health Organization) Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC)/Defined Daily Doses (DDD) methodology and expressed in DDD /1000 inhabitants /day (DID). Consumption was also analyzed using the WHO AwaRe (Access, Watch, Reserve) classification. Total (outpatients and hospital care) antibacterial use was 17.5 DID in 2014 and 24.7 DID in 2023. The top 5 antibacterial subgroups (ATC level 3) in 2023 were: penicillins, ATC group J01C (9.0 DID, 37.0% of all antibacterials); macrolides, lincosamides, streptogramins, ATC group J01F (5.3 DID, 21%), other beta-lactam antibacterials, ATC group J01D (4.4 DID, 18%); quinolones, ATC group J01M (2.5 DID, 10%) and tetracyclines, ATC group J01A (1.5 DID, 6%). The top 3 antibacterials (ATC level 5) in 2023 were: amoxicillin and enzyme inhibitor, azithromycin and amoxicillin. During the Covid-19 pandemic, there was an increase in the consumption of antibiotics from the Watch group. Again in 2022. and 2023. Bosnia and Herzegovina had met the WHO target of at least 60% of total consumption being Access agents. The increase consumption of antimicrobial drugs in the previous decade indicates the necessity of managing the consumption of existing antibacterial drugs.

Key words: antimicrobial drugs, consumption, azithromycin

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE MONITORING IN ANIMALS AND FOOD IN MONTENEGRO

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The aim of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) monitoring in zoonotic and commensal bacteria in animals and food in Montenegro is to support the process of determining trends and sources of resistance and support decision makers in Montenegro and in the EU in interventions to reduce AMR and protect public health. Annual AMR monitoring have been introduced since 2023, in accordance with the methodology outlined in Decision (EU) 2020/1729. In 2023, 41 caecal content from domestically produced fattening pigs at slaughterhouse and 44 fresh meat samples from pigs and bovine from retail and border control points (BCPs) have been collected and tested for isolates *Salmonella* spp. and commensal *E. coli*. 4 *Salmonella* spp. have been isolated (3 *S. Mbandaka* and one isolate *S. Typhimurium*), all from the caecal content. None of the isolates showed AMR. Commensal *E. coli* have been isolated from 45 samples, 41 isolates from caecal content from fattening pigs and 4 isolates from fresh pig and bovine meat. Most isolates (24) were resistant to tetracycline, ciprofloxacin (17) and sulfamethoxazole (17). High resistance is also found to trimethoprim (14) and nalidixic acid (14). None of the isolates were resistant to amikacin, colistin, meropenem and tigecycline. One isolate was resistant to cefotaxime and ceftazidime, therefore tested additionally on second panel of antimicrobials cefepime, cefotaxime and ceftazidime. In 2024, 107 caecal content at slaughterhouse samples from domestically produced broilers, 27 broilers and 8 turkey fresh meat samples from BCPs and 83 broiler and 10 turkey fresh meat samples from retail have been collected and tested for isolates *Salmonella* spp. and commensal *E. coli*. *Salmonella* spp. isolates collected from 108 samples of transport crates, 67 feces and 71 boot swabs have been also tested for AMR. Total number of 36 *Salmonella* spp. isolates have been tested on AMR (20 *S. Enteritidis*, 10 *S. Typhimurium*, 5 *S. Senftenberg* and 1 *S. Infantis*). Most isolates were resistant to tetracycline, sulfamethoxazole, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim and ampicillin. None of the isolates were resistant to amikacin, colistin, meropenem, tigecycline, cefotaxime and ceftazidime. 183 commensal *E. coli* have been collected from caecal content, fresh poultry meat from BCPs and retail samples. Most isolates, as in *Salmonella* spp. isolates were resistant to tetracycline, sulfamethoxazole, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim and ampicillin. 5 isolates from caecal content, 11 isolates from fresh meat from retail and 3 isolates from BCPs have been resistant to cefotaxime and ceftazidime. None of the isolates were resistant to amikacin, colistin, meropenem and tigecycline. Similar level of resistance to selected antimicrobials have been found in all species tested (pigs, broilers, turkeys, bovine). The results show high resistance to ciprofloxacin (fluoroquinolone), as well as some resistance to cefotaxime and ceftazidime (3rd-generation cephalosporins with beta lactamase inhibitors) that EMA classified as antibiotics to restrict in animals, due to their importance for humans in all species tested. The highest resistance to tetracycline sulfamethoxazole, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim and ampicillin correlates with national data on consumption in animals.

Key words: AMR, monitoring, Montenegro, results, animals, food

Acknowledgments: Testing and reporting is done by the Specialistic Veterinary Laboratory in Montenegro (SVL).

OPTIMIZING ANTIBIOTIC USE THROUGH INDIVIDUALIZED TREATMENT STRATEGIES

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The overuse and misuse of antibiotics remain major contributors to the rise of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), a global public health threat. In response, optimizing antibiotic use has become a critical focus of modern healthcare, with individualized treatment strategies emerging as a promising approach to enhance safety, efficacy and minimize the risks of AMR. When prescribing antibiotics, whether empirical or targeted, the optimal result is achieved if the selection of the antimicrobial drug takes into account all individual characteristics of the patient. The individualized antibiotic therapy emphasizes the importance of tailoring treatment to factors such as age, comorbidities, microbiome composition, genetic predispositions, and infection specifics. Moreover, a personalized medicine, which involves pharmacogenomic insights, can support decisions on drug selection, dosing, and duration, ensuring more precise and effective treatments. Individualisation of antibiotic therapy is particularly important in vulnerable populations, such as pediatric and geriatric populations, patients with impaired liver and kidney function, etc. Children present unique pharmacokinetic challenges; proportional dose reductions based on adult regimens are often inadequate. Moreover, only 20-30% of drugs have an approved pediatric license. On the other hand, interindividual variability and the incidence of adverse effects and drug interactions significantly increase in the elderly population. Recent advances in clinical pharmacology, particularly therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) and population-based pharmacokinetic modeling, have further reinforced the value of individualized therapy. These tools help clinicians to predict drug concentrations and response patterns, enabling dose adjustments that maximize therapeutic outcomes. To illustrate this, we investigated the interindividual variability in vancomycin pharmacokinetics within the neonatal population. Namely, neonates have immature renal function, leading to slower clearance of vancomycin. A standard adult-derived dose may result in toxic levels. Population pharmacokinetic models and TDM are strongly suggested to calculate individualized dosing regimens that achieve therapeutic levels while minimizing toxicity. Furthermore, in order to achieve the most favorable clinical outcome in the prevention and treatment of infections, with minimal toxicity to the patient and minimal risk of resistance, the concept and procedure of antibiotic stewardship have been introduced. This involves optimal selection of antibiotics, the optimal dosage of the selected antibiotic, and the optimal duration of therapy. This presentation highlights the significant interindividual variability in the applied antibiotic therapy in vulnerable populations and the role of clinical pharmacist, with a particular focus on recommendations regarding the pediatric and geriatric populations. Optimizing antibiotic use through individualized treatment strategies offers a promising pathway to combat AMR, improving both the immediate care of patients and the long-term effectiveness of antibiotics.

Key words: antibiotics, antimicrobial resistance, individualized therapy, antibiotic stewardship.

ZOONOTIC ZONES: TRACKING ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE BEHIND ZOO BARS

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents a critical global health challenge that transcends species and environmental boundaries. In zoological settings, where humans, domestic animals, wildlife, and environmental factors interact closely, the risk of AMR emergence and spread is particularly significant. Despite the recognized importance and increasing relevance of this issue, particularly in the context of One Health, the current body of research on AMR in zoo animals remains limited. Zoo animals are often treated with antimicrobial agents to prevent or manage infections, which, alongside shared habitats and close proximity among species and caretakers, creates favorable conditions for horizontal transmission of resistant microorganisms. From an One Health perspective, which emphasizes the interconnected health of people, animals, and the environment, zoos serve as unique ecosystems where AMR can evolve and disseminate. Due to the high diversity and density of animal species and their close cohabitation within relatively confined spaces, zoos may function as a 'melting pot' for antimicrobial resistance, facilitating the exchange and persistence of resistant bacteria across species barriers. This means that resistant bacteria and resistance genes can be exchanged between captive animals, zoo personnel, visitors, and even surrounding wildlife or natural habitats through direct contact, contaminated surfaces, or waste runoff. Many zoos contribute to wildlife conservation through breeding and reintroduction programs, as well as the rehabilitation of injured individuals and those confiscated from illegal trade; however, these activities may also contribute to the transmission of AMR bacteria, through the spread of AMR among zoos and into natural ecosystems worldwide. Diverse microbial communities, together with a multitude of environmental and anthropogenic factors, provide a fertile ground for the emergence and dissemination of both acquired and often neglected intrinsic antimicrobial resistance in so-called superbugs, which pose critical pathogenic threats to humans and animals alike, representing one of the most urgent global challenges from a One Health perspective. Implementing comprehensive AMR monitoring programs within zoos, including microbial testing, antimicrobial stewardship protocols, and environmental hygiene measures, is essential. These efforts not only protect the health of captive animals and staff but also contribute to broader public health and biodiversity conservation goals. As such, zoological institutions can play a pivotal role in AMR research and education, supporting the global fight against antimicrobial resistance through the lens of One Health.

Keywords: Antibiotic Resistance, Wild Animals, Zoos, One Health

Acknowledgment: Grant number: 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200117.

WILD RODENTS AS RESERVOIRS OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE: CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS FOR THE ONE HEALTH CONCEPT

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a pressing global threat to human, animal, and environmental health. While clinical and agricultural sources of AMR have been widely investigated, the role of wildlife, particularly wild rodents, has received considerably less attention. Due to their high adaptability, ubiquity in both rural and urban ecosystems, and close association with human settlements and livestock, wild rodents serve as critical reservoirs and vectors of AMR. Species such as *Rattus norvegicus* exhibit behaviors such as neophobia (avoidance of novel objects) and metacognition, which hinder effective population control and complicate epidemiological studies. Recent studies (2023–2024) indicate that urban rodents often harbor a higher abundance and diversity of AMR genes, including carbapenemase and colistin resistance determinants. Mechanisms of AMR dissemination include horizontal gene transfer through plasmids and integrons, and environmental shedding via feces. Data from several European countries confirm the presence of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, MRSA, and vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE) in wild rodent populations. In Croatia, although systematic monitoring is lacking, sporadic outbreaks involving these pathogens have occurred in healthcare settings over the past decade. The proximity of rodent habitats to waste sites and hospitals suggests a potential epidemiological link in AMR transmission across species. Advanced metagenomic tools now allow for culture-independent profiling of resistomes in rodent microbiota, offering new insights into the environmental dimension of AMR ecology. Incorporating rodents into national surveillance frameworks and adopting a One Health approach are essential for a comprehensive understanding of AMR dynamics and the development of effective mitigation strategies.

Key words: antimicrobial resistance, wild rodents, One Health

FEED QUALITY AND SAFETY: CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

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Modern feed production, an important link in the entire food chain, is crucial in creating sustainable food systems. By optimizing feed efficiency and incorporating alternative protein sources, the industry can significantly reduce its environmental impact. This not only ensures the health of livestock but also contributes to the overall resilience of food supply networks. Ultimately, these advancements in feed production can lead to healthier ecosystems and improved food security for communities worldwide. This transition will require collaboration among farmers, researchers, and policymakers, as well as a commitment to education and awareness about sustainable practices. By working together, they can foster a culture that prioritizes environmental stewardship while meeting the growing demands for food. As we move forward, it is essential to continuously innovate and adapt to changing conditions, ensuring that strategies remain effective and inclusive. Productivity, efficiency, environmental sustainability, and feed safety are greatly impacted by the creation and use of a wide variety of new feed additives, improvements in feed processing machinery, and developments in animal nutrition. The feed industry faces significant challenges caused by the expanding global population and rising consumer demand, especially in lowering feed costs while optimizing production efficiency. The investigation of substitute raw materials, the development of technological equipment, the incorporation of new technologies, the use of natural additives (as antibiotic substitutes), and the automation and digitization of feed management are important areas for progress in the animal feed industry. Contemporary animal feed needs to be safe, nutrient-dense and adapted to the needs of both consumers and animals. Today, consumers are becoming more aware of the quality and safety of animal products like meat, eggs, and milk. Because they see feed as an essential link in the food production chain that directly affects human nutrition, they are curious about the raising of animals and the food they are fed. For ethical and sustainable animal production, feed safety is essential. Protecting animal health, enhancing animal welfare, and preserving public health depends on feed being free of contaminants like mycotoxins, pathogens, heavy metals, and veterinary medication residues. To ensure feed safety, quality control, traceability, and regulatory compliance are essential throughout the feed supply chain. Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) and Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) are obligatory standards in contemporary feed mills. Reducing the use of antibiotics in humans and animals has received particular attention in recent decades to stop the development of resistance in microorganisms. The ongoing pressure on livestock operations to reduce the use of antibiotics is a top priority among the demands for more natural inputs. Demand for "raised without antibiotics" (RWA) production is also rising. Many options for biologically based feed additives, such as those that either replace or increase productivity, can support the reduction of antibiotic use in RWA systems. The term "natural growth promoters" (NGPs) is used to describe these solutions, as they improve animal performance in a natural and consumer-acceptable way. Ensuring sustainable feed quality and safety requires ongoing innovation, technological advancement, and collaboration across the supply chain to meet rising demand, reduce environmental impact, and protect animal and human health.

Key words: feed, quality, safety, contaminants, antibiotics

IDENTIFICATION AND CONTROL OF CHEMICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL HAZARD IN FOOD AND FEED

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The identification and control of chemical and microbiological hazards in food and feed is a crucial component of food safety systems, particularly in the context of Serbia's harmonization with European Union legislation. This paper presents an overview of the current status, regulatory framework, and control measures implemented in Serbia to manage food and feed safety risks. The chemical hazards discussed include pesticide residues, veterinary drug residues, mycotoxins, and heavy metals, while microbiological hazards focus on pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Escherichia coli*. Data from national monitoring programs and official controls conducted over the past five years are analyzed to assess compliance trends and risk areas. The integration of risk-based approaches in inspection and sampling procedures has contributed to improved targeting of high-risk products and operators. Furthermore, the implementation of the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) system across the food production chain is discussed, including challenges in small- and medium-sized enterprises. Capacity building of competent authorities, laboratory infrastructure development, and international cooperation through EU pre-accession assistance and twinning projects have significantly supported the strengthening of the national food safety system. This paper highlights the importance of a science-based approach to risk assessment, the role of national reference laboratories, and continuous improvement of surveillance systems in ensuring food and feed safety. Recommendations are provided for enhancing data collection, stakeholder communication, and preparedness for EU membership obligations.

Key words: food safety, hazard control, Serbia, chemical hazards, microbiological hazards

Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge the support of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management.

MYCOTOXINS IN MAIZE: IMPACTS ON FOOD AND FEED SAFETY ACROSS ITS PRODUCTION CHAIN

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Mycotoxins, toxic fungal metabolites, represent an increasingly urgent challenge both in Serbia and globally, with their prevalence rising significantly due to the climate change. These compounds pose serious health risks to humans and animals, including carcinogenic, immunosuppressive, teratogenic, and other harmful effects. Over the past two decades, Serbia has been particularly affected by climate changes, marked by rising air temperatures, a growing number of tropical days, and more frequent occurrences of heatwaves and droughts. Maize, the most widely cultivated crop in the country, has been the most significantly affected by climate changes. Prolonged hot and dry periods have not only caused significant reductions in maize yield and productivity, but have also led to a multi-annual increase in the risk of mycotoxin contamination. Such weather conditions have been particularly favorable for *the Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* species, resulting in the synthesis of aflatoxins and fumonisins. Over the past thirteen years, aflatoxins have contaminated between 24% and 84% of maize samples harvested in eight different years, while fumonisins have been detected in over 85% of samples in nearly every year. In addition to aflatoxins and fumonisins, several dozen other mycotoxins and fungal metabolites have been detected in maize samples over the years. During the same period, high levels of aflatoxins in maize used for animal feed have frequently led to elevated contamination of milk and dairy products with aflatoxin M1. Moreover, as a staple food and a key component of animal feed, contaminated maize has contributed to the wider contamination of various products, significantly impacting food and feed safety throughout the production chain, including both plant- and animal-based products. The persistence of this issue over more than a decade underscores not only public health risks but also the broader economic and trade-related consequences for Serbia’s agricultural sector. According to climate change projections, maize is expected to face its highest risk by the middle of the 21st century, as a result of escalating climate-induced pressures on crop production. It is therefore essential to urgently strengthen monitoring systems, invest in climate-resilient agricultural practices, and raise awareness of how climate change affects food and feed safety and economic resilience, in order to ensure the future sustainability of maize production and protect public health in Serbia and beyond.

Key words: maize, mycotoxins, food and feed safety, climate change

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by The Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (451-03-136/2025-03/200222).

MYCOTOXINS IN ANIMAL FEED IN SERBIA: STATUS, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

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Mycotoxins, toxic secondary metabolites produced by fungi, pose a persistent threat to animal health and food safety worldwide. In Serbia, climatic conditions, inadequate storage, and suboptimal crop handling practices significantly contribute to the frequent occurrence of mycotoxins, particularly aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) and deoxynivalenol (DON), in animal feed. This study provides an overview of the current status of mycotoxin contamination in Serbian maize, based on monitoring data from 2010 to 2024. The data indicate significant annual variability in contamination levels, largely driven by seasonal weather extremes such as drought and high temperatures, particularly during critical crop growth stages. The most severe AFB1 contamination was recorded in 2012, when 97% of maize samples tested positive and 65% exceeded EU regulatory limits. Similarly high contamination levels occurred in 2013 and 2014, with up to 95% of samples testing positive. For DON, the peak was observed in 2014, when all tested samples were contaminated, with concentrations reaching 9.498 mg/kg, well above both EU and national thresholds. In contrast, recent data show some improvement. In 2023, 56% of maize samples were positive for AFB1, with 6% exceeding EU limits. For DON, 72% of samples tested positive, all exceeding permissible levels. In 2024, AFB1 remained a concern: 48% of samples were positive, and 59% of these exceeded EU limits. DON, however, was not detected in any tested samples. These results highlight the urgent need for year-round mycotoxin risk management. Priorities should include preventive agronomic practices, improved storage, use of mycotoxin absorbents, and robust regulatory monitoring. The national laboratory infrastructure plays a critical role in maintaining feed safety and supporting data-driven interventions. Looking forward, an integrated approach combining farmer education, predictive modeling, advanced analytical techniques, and strong policy support is essential to mitigate mycotoxin risks and ensure sustainable livestock production in Serbia.

Key words: Aflatoxin B1, Deoxynivalenol, Maize contamination, Feed safety, Mycotoxin monitoring

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research of Vojvodina, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia (contract number: 003057154 2024 09418 003 000 000 001/2).

WHEN THE CURE BECOMES THE CONTAMINANT: RESIDUES OF VETERINARY MEDICINAL PRODUCTS IN HONEY

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Improper use of veterinary medicinal products in treating bee colonies can lead to contamination of honey with their residues, posing potential health risks to consumers, including antimicrobial resistance. This overview of veterinary medicinal product residues in honey is based on the Rapid Alert System on Food and Feed (RASFF; 1999–2024), the official EU monitoring programs (2022–2023), and data retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS; 2015–2024). RASFF reported 272 notifications, of which 19.5% were classified as alert, most frequently for honey from China (23.9%). Sulfonamides were the most numerous (30.4%, max 39.5 mg/kg), followed by amphenicols (18.6%, max 4.43 mg/kg) and aminoglycosides (14.9%, max 1.3 mg/kg). Individually present residues totaled 220 cases, most frequently sulfonamides (63), then amphenicols (46) > aminoglycosides (32) > macrolides (23) > tetracyclines (21) > nitrofurans derivatives (20). Simultaneous presence of up to 5 residues was recorded in 49 cases, most often a combination of two sulfonamides. However, in the last decade, only 19 notifications were recorded: chloramphenicol (7) >> dapsone, dihydrostreptomycin, metronidazole, sulfonamide (unspecified), tetracycline (2 each) > ciprofloxacin, enrofloxacin, sulfathiazole, sulfadimidine, streptomycin, doxycycline, trimethoprim, semicarbazide (1 each). The EU monitoring Report for 2023 included 3422 samples analyzed for presence of pharmacologically active substances, revealing 14 (0.41%) non-compliant samples; 3 (0.12%) for substances prohibited or unauthorized in food-producing animals (Group A) and 11 (0.47%; 19 non-compliant results) for authorized substances (Group B; subgroup B1 - antibacterials, including antibiotics, sulfonamides, and quinolones). Of the 3056 samples analyzed in 2022, 42 (1.37%) were non-compliant (97 non-compliant results, all for Group B substances, of which 21 samples/42 results for subgroup B1). WoS studies identified tetracyclines (serious environmental problems) and aminoglycosides (effects on human intestinal microflora) as the most commonly detected residues in honey, followed by sulfonamides (mild toxicity to blood cells), fluoroquinolones (transfer of resistant zoonotic bacteria, in particular *Salmonella* spp. and *Campylobacter* spp., from animals to humans), and macrolides (drug-drug interactions); only sporadic samples contained nitroimidazoles. The tetracycline group included tetracycline (0.07–65.2 µg/kg), oxytetracycline (0.03–50.55 µg/kg), and metacycline. Among aminoglycosides, streptomycin (0.06–59.9 µg/kg), dihydrostreptomycin (9.94–992.58 µg/kg, maximum level in honey from Turkey), gentamicin, kanamycin, amikacin, and neomycin were detected. Representatives of sulfonamides were sulfadimidine (2.16–196.51 µg/kg), sulfamethoxazole, sulfamethizole, and sulfathiazole. Fluoroquinolones included ciprofloxacin (3.16–8.31 µg/kg), enrofloxacin, sparfloxacin, and norfloxacin. Macrolides were represented with erythromycin and tulathromycin, while metronidazole was the only nitroimidazole. Promoting responsible veterinary practices in apiculture, strengthening monitoring systems, and international cooperation are essential risk management options in protecting public health.

Keywords: food safety, monitoring program, public health, RASFF, risk assessment

FOODBORNE BACTERIAL BIOFILMS AS SELF-PROTECTIVE MECHANISMS OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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Food safety is a major global concern, as foodborne pathogens pose serious risk to public health and threaten food security. This review aims to elucidate the role of biofilms in enhancing antimicrobial resistance, thereby contributing to the persistence and resilience of these pathogens within the food production and supply chain. Biofilm is a three-dimensional aggregated community of microorganisms embedded in sticky extracellular polysaccharide matrix. The formation of biofilm is a process that involves initial attachment of bacterial cells to a substrate followed by their irreversible attachment and formation of micro colony, biofilm maturation and active or passive dispersal of bacterial cells. Released bacterial cells can contaminate food and different surfaces, and/or colonize distant sites and form new biofilms. Foodborne bacteria that have demonstrated resistance to antibiotics, such as *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Campylobacter* spp., and *Yersinia enterocolitica*, can emerge and spread from farm to table. All those bacteria may form biofilms in the food processing environments as a survival and adaptive strategy. Biofilms provide bacteria with enhanced tolerance and resistance to many different stressors. The mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance of foodborne bacterial biofilms include, among others, limited antibiotic penetration due to the extracellular polysaccharide matrix. The interaction of antibiotics with the extracellular polysaccharide matrix and slowed diffusion lowers their activity. Once inside biofilms, antibiotics face challenge due to genetic changes in the bacterial cells or the masking of their target sites. Further, defense mechanisms include extrusion of antibiotics using efflux pumps, adaptive stress responses, and reduced growth rates. Deep in the inner layers of biofilm, metabolic byproducts, waste materials and nutrients accumulate, resulting in altered metabolic activity of bacterial cells in nutrient-limited microenvironments, changes in their gene expression and the development of persister cells. Persister cells are a small population of bacteria that enter spore-like state as an act of survival in which they are resistant to extreme conditions. All these mechanisms enable foodborne bacteria to escape from antibiotics and to survive in high concentration of antibiotics. Bacterial cells embedded in biofilm can tolerate antibiotic concentrations ten to 1000 times higher than planktonic bacteria cells. Antibiotic resistance in foodborne pathogens is significantly influenced by globalization and international trade. The global movement of food products facilitates the dissemination of antibiotic-resistant bacteria across borders, making it a critical factor in the worldwide spread of resistance. Studies have shown that the use of antibiotics in agriculture, animal husbandry and aquaculture for preventive, therapeutic and/or growth-promoting reasons can lead to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, which can then spread to humans through the food chain. Therefore, future research and collaboration among different sectors at national, regional and international levels are needed to understand bacterial biofilm formation mechanisms and to develop solutions for antimicrobial resistance combat.

Key words: foodborne bacteria, food contamination, biofilm, antibiotics

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

DISINFECTANT ACTIVITY ON BIOFILM FORMATION AND AGAINST MATURE BIOFILM OF *SALMONELLA* SPP. ISOLATED FROM ANIMAL-ORIGINATED FOOD

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Salmonella spp. are extremely significant bacteria within the "One Health" concept due to their ability to colonise and infect various animal and plant hosts, as well as humans. Biofilm formation allows *Salmonella* to survive between various hosts and exist in the external environment. Biofilm represents a highly organised bacterial sessile community embedded within a polysaccharide matrix, produced by bacteria only during biofilm formation. Biofilm is very resistant to antimicrobial drugs and can only be removed through physical means, such as thorough cleaning and treatment with high concentrations of chemical substances that may have a toxic effect. Our goal was to determine the disinfectant activity on mature, preformed biofilm, as well as its potency to prevent biofilm formation. In our study, we included 70 strains of *Salmonella* spp. isolated from animal-origin foods (primarily chicken, minced beef and milk products). Biofilm production was tested using the crystal dye method in microtiter plates with overnight bacterial incubation at 25°C and 37°C in brain heart infusion broth. The disinfectants used in this experiment were hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), bleach (NaOCl), and benzalkonium chloride (BAC). To examine the activity of disinfectants in preventing biofilm formation, we utilised doubly decreasing concentrations (7-0.01% for H₂O₂, and 1.25-0.001% for bleach and BAC) during overnight incubation with the bacterial inoculum at 25°C and 37°C. In order to determine disinfectants' efficiency against mature biofilm, we used 0.5% bleach and BAC, and 3% H₂O₂ for 5 minutes of treatment after bacterial incubation and biofilm formation at 25°C and 37°C. Statistically significant difference was observed between the effects of all three biocides in biofilm prevention, 0.15% for BAH, 0.07% for NaOCl and 0.02% for H₂O₂ (p<0.001, p<0.001, p<0.001) during incubation at 37°C. At a temperature of 25°C, it was observed that H₂O₂ (0.07%) had a significantly better activity in preventing the formation of biofilms than NaOCl (0.12%) and BAC (0.17%) (p<0.001), while BAC and NaOCl had equal effectiveness (p=0.06). The treatment of all three biocides on mature biofilm formed at 25°C demonstrated significant eradication of the biofilm, with NaOCl showing substantially higher effectiveness compared to BAH and H₂O₂ (p=0.001, p=0.006), which exhibited similar effects (p=0.61). When comparing the effectiveness of these three biocides on biofilm formed at 37°C, the results were consistent with those at 25°C; that is, NaOCl displayed significantly better activity in eradicating the biofilm (p=0.003, p=0.006) compared to the other two biocides, which showed similar activity (p=0.86). Our results show a significant difference in the activity of various disinfectants when we consider the entire process of biofilm formation, i.e. H₂O₂ has the greatest ability to prevent biofilm formation, while bleach showed the highest efficacy in the eradication of mature, preformed biofilm of *Salmonella* spp.

Key words: *Salmonella*, biofilm, disinfectants

SALMONELLA IN ANIMAL FEED: THE ROLE OF BIOFILM IN BACTERIAL SURVIVAL AND SPREAD

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Animal feed is considered the initial link in the "farm-to-fork" food chain, and its microbiological safety plays a crucial role in preserving both animal and human health. However, in practice, it often receives less attention compared to food intended for human consumption. Animal feed serves as a gateway for foodborne pathogens to enter the food chain, with *Salmonella* spp. being of particular importance due to its zoonotic potential and significant impact on food safety, human and animal health, and the substantial economic consequences of salmonellosis in both human and veterinary medicine worldwide. One of the key factors that enables *Salmonella* to survive under the demanding conditions of feed production, storage, and transport is the formation of multicellular communities known as biofilms. The aim of this study was to identify the *Salmonella* serovars Enteritidis, Infantis, Hadar, Virchow, and Typhimurium in animal feed—whose presence is legally prohibited in animals in the Republic of Serbia—and to assess their biofilm-forming ability as well as their susceptibility to commonly used antibiotics, which is particularly relevant for biosafety in production. In this study, two different methods were used to assess the biofilm-forming ability of *Salmonella* spp. isolates: a quantitative microtiter plate assay using crystal violet staining, and the Congo Red agar test. In addition, differences in morphotypes among isolates of the same serovar were analyzed, with a focus on their biofilm-forming capabilities. Out of 54 *Salmonella* isolates obtained from animal feed, serological typing identified three relevant serovars: *S. Enteritidis* (n = 9; 16.67%), *S. Infantis* (n = 8; 14.82%), and *S. Typhimurium* (n = 2; 3.70%). Colony morphology on Congo Red agar revealed that 100% of the isolates formed biofilms, with 73.7% of them (*S. Enteritidis* n = 7; *S. Infantis* n = 5; *S. Typhimurium* n = 2) forming the RDAR morphotype, while 26.3% (*S. Enteritidis* n = 2; *S. Infantis* n = 3) formed the PDAR morphotype. Based on optical density measurements and established cut-off values, all isolates were capable of forming biofilms: 8 *S. Enteritidis* and 6 *S. Infantis* isolates were classified as strong biofilm producers, while all *S. Typhimurium* isolates, along with 2 *S. Infantis* and 1 *S. Enteritidis* isolate, were moderate producers. A comparison of the two biofilm assessment methods showed differences between strains and serovars, as well as within the same serovar. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing using the disk diffusion method according to CLSI guidelines showed that all tested isolates were sensitive to all 14 antibiotics, including: amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, ampicillin, cephalosporins, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, gentamicin, nalidixic acid, streptomycin, sulfonamides, and tetracyclines. The confirmed ability of these isolates to form biofilms further highlights the importance of *Salmonella* spp. as a serious threat in the animal feed production chain, since biofilms significantly hinder the elimination of bacteria using conventional disinfection methods. The results of this study may contribute to a better understanding of the contamination risks associated with animal feed, which is essential for protecting animal health and reducing risks throughout the human food chain.

Keywords: animal feed, *Salmonella*, biofilm, resistance.

Acknowledgement: This work was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* STRAINS ISOLATED FROM BOVINE MASTITIS – THEN AND NOW

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Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*) is widely recognized in the dairy sector for its ability to cause both clinical and subclinical mastitis. In addition to this, some strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* are also capable of producing heat-stable enterotoxins, which can lead to serious foodborne intoxications in humans. Therefore, controlling this bacterium throughout the food production chain is essential not only for animal health, but also for overall food safety. More than a decade ago, a study conducted on dairy farms in central Serbia and Vojvodina resulted in the isolation of 75 *S. aureus* strains from bovine udders. Antimicrobial susceptibility to ten agents was assessed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method. All strains were sensitive to amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, novobiocin, tetracycline, and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole. Resistance to bacitracin was observed in 67 strains (89.33%), to penicillin in 13 (17.33%), to ampicillin in 4 (5.33%), and to amoxicillin in 3 strains (4.00%). Most isolates were resistant to only one antimicrobial agent. Eight isolates (12.90%), all from cows with subclinical mastitis, showed no resistance. The two most resistant isolates, from cows with clinical mastitis, were resistant to four of the ten tested antimicrobial agents. One of the key findings was the detection of the *mecA* gene in one isolate. Despite accumulated knowledge, official recommendations, and the introduction of alternative control measures, antimicrobial resistance remains a growing global health challenge. While there is a well-established correlation between antibiotic use in livestock and the development of resistance, several studies emphasize that the overuse of antibiotics in human medicine also plays a major role. The increasing prevalence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is particularly alarming, especially on farms operating under intensive production systems. Recent research indicates increasing interest in alternative strategies for mastitis management. Diagnostic innovations, such as biosensors and real-time milk monitoring systems, enable early, non-invasive detection. Therapeutic alternatives include phytotherapy, probiotics, essential oils, homeopathy, immunomodulators, and physical methods such as udder massage and heat therapy. These approaches may help reduce antibiotic use and improve treatment outcomes. Major factors currently driving antimicrobial resistance include the irresponsible use of antibiotics in livestock (especially for prophylaxis), group treatments in intensive systems, use of antibiotics in feed, and global movement of people and animals, which facilitates the spread of resistant strains. In conclusion, antimicrobial resistance remains one of the most urgent global challenges - not only in veterinary medicine but also in public health. Combating resistance requires prudent antibiotic use in both human and veterinary sectors, supported by continuous education of healthcare professionals, veterinarians, farmers, and all stakeholders involved in antibiotic administration. Further development of alternative therapies and preventive strategies for conditions such as mastitis is essential. Sustained research efforts are needed to better understand how to reduce antibiotic use in livestock and to curb the spread of highly resistant strains already in circulation.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), antibiotic usage, dairy cattle, mastitis, public health

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No: 451-03-137/2025-03/200117 and Grant No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200143)

IMPLICATIONS FOR MILK SAFETY: WITHDRAWAL PERIOD OF AN ESSENTIAL OIL-BASED FORMULATION FOR THE MASTITIS TREATMENT IN DAIRY COWS

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With growing interest in the natural alternatives to antibiotics for managing bovine mastitis, essential oil-based treatments offer promising therapeutic potential. However, their safe integration into dairy practice requires clear evidence regarding residue and appropriate withdrawal periods. This study assesses the residue kinetics of thymol and carvacrol - key constituents of Phyto-Bomat, a veterinary pharmaceutical formulation composed of essential oils from *Thymus vulgaris*, *Thymus serpyllum*, *Origanum vulgare*, and *Satureja montana*, combined with oil macerates of marigold and St. John’s wort. The formulation, administered intramammarily at a dose of 15 mL twice daily over five consecutive days, was tested in lactating cows affected by both clinical and subclinical mastitis to evaluate residue levels and support the establishment of safe usage guidelines. Residue levels in milk and plasma were analyzed using a gas chromatography–mass spectrometry technique (GC-MS) method. Phyto-Bomat treatment resulted in low milk residues of thymol and carvacrol, with concentrations ranging from 0.04 to 0.37 µg/mL. Concentrations peaked within 12 hours and returned to baseline within 24 hours. Plasma levels showed a similar time-dependent pattern, with detectable residues still present after 24 hours. The study demonstrates that Phyto-Bomat treatment results in low, short-lived residues in milk, posing no risk to consumer safety or product quality. These findings support the establishment of a short withdrawal period and highlight the formulation’s viability as a residue-safe alternative for mastitis therapy. The results further underscore the potential of essential oil-based treatments to promote safe and effective mastitis management, aligning with the principles of antimicrobial stewardship and current trends toward more sustainable dairy production.

Keywords: cows, essential oils, mastitis, Phyto-Bomat, residues

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, PROMIS, #GRANT no. 6066966, InfoBomat, and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Contract no. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117 and 451-03-136/2025-03/200222].

FIRST DAYS, LASTING IMPACT – ANTIBIOTIC-FREE BROILER FARMING

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Poultry production is one of the most widespread food industries in the world, and chicken is the most commonly raised species, with over 90 billion tons of chicken meat produced annually. Also, poultry is one of the most consumed meats worldwide, being the second most produced and consumed meat in the European Union after pork. The main reasons for this interest in chicken meat are the relatively low production costs and the lack of cultural and religious restrictions on its consumption. In 2010, approximately 63,200 tons of antibiotics were used in the global livestock industry. Projections suggest that by 2030, this figure will rise to 105,600 tons, driven by the increasing demand for animal products resulting from global population growth. A substantial proportion of these antibiotics are used specifically in poultry production. The extensive and often irrational use of antibiotics has contributed to the emergence of antimicrobial-resistant (AMR) bacteria. The development of resistant pathogens not only leads to economic losses but also poses a serious threat to both human and animal health. The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified antimicrobial resistance as one of the top ten global public health threats in its five-year strategic plan. Similarly, the United Nations has recognized AMR as one of the most pressing challenges facing the global community. If appropriate preventive measures are not implemented during the production, processing, and marketing of poultry products, chicken meat and eggs may become contaminated with infectious agents capable of causing disease in humans. Several studies have investigated the presence of antibiotic-resistant microorganisms, considered critical to human health, in the gut microbiota of day-old chicks. Moreover, there is clear scientific evidence that day-old chicks can harbor antibiotic resistance genes. Multidrug-resistant bacteria, silently carried by these chicks, may represent a significant reservoir of resistance, contributing to the transmission of AMR to humans via the food chain. These resistant strains may disseminate in the environment or be directly transmitted to humans, potentially resulting in adverse health outcomes. This manuscript presents data on the most commonly isolated bacterial species in day-old chicks, as well as their resistance to antimicrobial drugs, based on investigations conducted on poultry farms in the Province of Vojvodina. As a potential solution to this growing problem, it is essential to implement and maintain strict internal and external biosecurity measures, ensure high standards of food and water quality, control microclimatic conditions, and adhere to effective vaccination protocols. Additionally, alternative strategies are being explored to reduce the reliance on antibiotics in poultry production. Considerable research efforts have been directed toward identifying natural compounds with growth-promoting and health-supporting properties, serving as potential substitutes for antibiotics. These alternatives aim to maintain low mortality rates and high productivity levels while safeguarding environmental integrity and public health. Among these, the most popular are probiotics, prebiotics, enzymes, organic acids, immunostimulants, bacteriocins, bacteriophages, phytogetic feed additives, phytoncides, nanoparticles, essential oils (EOs) and bacterial vaccines.

Key words: antibiotics, antimicrobial resistance, day-old chicks, phytobiotics, poultry

Acknowledgments: This study was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

ANTIMICROBIAL USE MONITORING GUIDELINES IN AQUACULTURE: TOOL FOR ESTABLISHING BASELINE DATASETS TO SUPPORT NATIONAL PROGRAMS FOR EMERGING ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PREVENTION AND CONTROL

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The primary reason and rationale for the use of antimicrobials in aquaculture is related to their value as interventions (treatments) to minimise disease burden, improve on the economy of the production, and support animal welfare. Prudent use of antimicrobials avoids or minimizes the risk of losses related to mortalities, reduced growth rates, and market value (unpleasant appearance or reduced shelf life). Antimicrobial use is adopted by both aquaculture producers and ornamental fish traders, especially in cases where standard management practices are not sufficient to prevent and control infectious disease outbreak. The expansion of aquaculture globally as a food production activity is faced with increasing challenges that affect aquatic environments, including the influx of AMR from land-based establishments such as effluent from AMU in human population, animal farms, and agriculture. This situation in turn suggests that a variety of entry points of antimicrobials into aquaculture establishments and the aquaculture food-value chain may need to be considered when discussing objectives of AMU field monitoring and exposure to antimicrobials beyond the sales-prescription data. Importantly, the monitoring objectives reflect major concerns related to the impact of AMU in aquatic animals on the emergence and spread of AMR in human beings, including the increased risk of AMR gene transmission in aquaculture compartments and surrounding aquatic and terrestrial environments as a result of these interventions.

Key words: Antimicrobial Resistance; Aquaculture; Monitoring; Data Processing; Use of antimicrobials

Acknowledgments: The presenting author acknowledges the work performed as part of the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH) working group for development of the guidelines to monitor antimicrobial use in aquaculture.

APPLICATION OF VETERINARY BIOSECURITY MEASURES IN LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION: A FOUNDATION FOR ANIMAL WELFARE PROTECTION, AND A CONTRIBUTION TO ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PREVENTION

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Modern intensive livestock production poses challenges to animal welfare and contributes to the development of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The aim of this review is to emphasize the importance of veterinary biosecurity measures in livestock production, especially their role in animal welfare protection and reducing AMR. Veterinary biosecurity measures are structured procedures designed to prevent the introduction and spread of infectious agents and are typically categorized as primary, secondary, and tertiary measures. Primary measures focus on preventing the entry of pathogens onto farms. Secondary measures aim to limit their spread within the farm and surrounding environment, while tertiary measures enhance animal resistance through vaccination and genetic selection. Complementary, the WASH concept (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene), originally developed in public health, can also be applied to livestock biosecurity, addressing waste management, hygiene protocols, and access to safe water for animals. All of these biosecurity measures can improve farm productivity and animal welfare by reducing mortality, enhancing feed conversion, and minimizing stress, disease outbreaks, and the need for invasive treatments. Moreover, by implementing effective farm biosecurity practices, the occurrence of disease outbreaks and infectious diseases in livestock production can be significantly reduced, resulting in a decrease in the need for antimicrobial treatments and reducing the risk of AMR development. In conclusion, biosecurity measures are not only a technical tool but a strategic framework for enhancing animal welfare and improving production. And, in the context of antimicrobial resistance, biosecurity measures are the most fundamental and long-term sustainable intervention available to the livestock sector. Therefore, the implementation of appropriate biosecurity measures across different production systems must be supported by national policies, continuous professional education, and an interdisciplinary approach involving veterinary medicine, public health, and agriculture.

Key words: antimicrobial resistance, biosecurity measures, livestock production, animal welfare

COMBATING AMR IN NORTH MACEDONIA: THE ROLE OF VETERINARY VACCINES

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Veterinary medicine is critical at the intersection of animal health, food safety, and public health. As a tightly regulated profession, veterinarians are tasked with the prevention and control of diseases in animals but also with safeguarding the quality of animal-derived food products through sustainable and responsible practices. A key area of concern in recent years has been the global rise in antimicrobial resistance (AMR), driven largely by the overuse and misuse of antibiotics in both human and veterinary medicine. With the effectiveness of antibiotics waning, the world now faces the looming threat of a post-antibiotic era, where common infections may once again become life-threatening. Recognising this urgent threat, the international community has mobilised to reduce antimicrobial use (AMU), particularly in agrifood systems. The 79th United Nations General Assembly issued a declaration targeting a substantial reduction in AMU by 2030, with 47 countries further committing, through the Muscat Manifesto, to cut AMU by 30–50% within the same timeframe. Achieving these targets will be especially challenging in regions where demand for livestock products is increasing due to population growth and rising incomes. Therefore, innovative, preventive strategies are essential. One of the most promising and underutilised tools in this fight is vaccination. Veterinary vaccines are essential for preventing infectious diseases in animals, reducing the need for antibiotics, and ultimately limiting the emergence and spread of resistant microorganisms. By reducing infection rates, vaccines not only enhance animal health and welfare but also contribute significantly to food security and public health, particularly by preventing zoonotic diseases that can be transmitted from animals to humans. Despite their proven effectiveness, veterinary vaccines remain underused in many parts of the world. Limited market access, delayed availability, and a general lack of awareness about the broader benefits of vaccination continue to hinder progress. Public understanding and professional commitment must be strengthened to achieve wider vaccine coverage and greater impact. This presentation explores the critical role of veterinary vaccines in combating antimicrobial resistance, highlighting their preventive potential and long-term economic and health benefits. It also delves into current trends within the European Union's veterinary vaccine market and presents an overview of the market landscape in the Republic of North Macedonia. As the world seeks sustainable solutions to AMR, vaccines offer a powerful, proactive path forward—one that must be prioritised and expanded.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance, veterinary vaccines, North Macedonia, animal health, antimicrobial use, AMR prevention

USE OF THE POULTRY PROBIOTIC *BACILLUS SUBTILIS* PS-216 TO FIGHT FOODBORNE PATHOGENS AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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The spread of resistant pathogenic bacteria in livestock production, and consequently in the food industry, is a serious global problem. Stricter regulations and health and economic concerns about the use of antibiotics have prompted research into alternative solutions, of which the use of probiotics is gaining in popularity. Knowledge of bacterial interactions is essential to develop better probiotics that limit pathogenic bacteria in the environment and hosts. Thus, the extensive research work on bacterial interactions of the beneficial bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* and foodborne pathogenic bacteria with the objective of effective probiotic development for pathogen control is presented. *In vitro* studies have been used to assess the anti-pathogen potential of *B. subtilis* in planktonic and biofilm coculture. *In vivo*, a chicken infection model has been used to assess the effect of *B. subtilis* spores in a concentration of 10⁹ spores/L of drinking water on the colonization of *Campylobacter jejuni* after the infection. Furthermore, the effects of *B. subtilis* spores on chicken performance and gut health (short chain fatty acids (SCFA) and microbiota) were assessed. *In vitro* studies addressing interactions between *B. subtilis* and foodborne pathogenic bacteria (*C. jejuni*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Listeria monocytogenes*) both sensitive and resistant to antibiotics, indicated a high probiotic potential of the *B. subtilis* PS-216 strain as the strain PS-216 significantly inhibits the growth of all three pathogens of high concern in biofilms and planktonic cultures. Moreover, the *in vivo* infection model experiment confirmed that PS-216 spores limit the presence of *C. jejuni* in broilers. This is highly important as broilers, among other poultry, are a common source of *C. jejuni* infections. Recently we also investigated the effects of *B. subtilis* PS-216 on broilers, its animal host. Improvements in growth and feed conversion (up to 5% improved in treated chicken), cecal microbiota and SCFA composition (shift to butyrate producers and increase in butyrate concentration in treated chicken) and meat quality were observed in broilers receiving the PS-216 spores. Overall, results suggest that *B. subtilis* PS-216 is a highly promising probiotic for chicken with potential for pathogen control in animals and the environment.

Key words: *Bacillus subtilis* PS-216, chicken probiotic, foodborne pathogens, bacterial interactions, gut microbiota, feed conversion improvement.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS) projects J4-50134 and J4-4550, and the national research program P4-0116.

A DECISION-MAKING APPROACH TO EVIDENCE-BASED TREATMENT OF NEONATAL CALF DIARRHEA SYNDROME

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Neonatal diarrhea syndrome (NDS) is the most common cause of illness and utilization of antibacterials in calves under 15 days of age. The primary infectious agents associated with the disease are enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* K99/F5, rotavirus A, bovine coronavirus, and *Cryptosporidium* spp., which either alone or in combination directly affect the intestinal epithelial cells, resulting in diarrhea. Regardless of the primary pathogen, diarrheic calves often develop secondary small intestinal overgrowth of *E. coli* bacteria, which delays recovery and increases the risk of bacteremia and death. In practice, antibacterial therapy is commonly recommended for the elimination of the causative agent and prevention of bacteremia. However, in most cases, the use of antibacterials is not justified because viral and parasitic agents are more likely to be involved, especially in calves older than five days. In addition, bacterial overgrowth and bacteremia occur in less than 1/3 of the diarrheic calves. This is not a prudent and responsible use of antimicrobials and increases the potential for antimicrobial resistance. In addition to bacteremia, diarrheic calves are also at risk of dehydration, electrolyte imbalance, acidosis and hypoglycemia. All these potential risks should be assessed and treated accordingly. Therefore, decision-making guidelines based on evidence from a thorough clinical examination are necessary for the effective treatment of NDS. The following evidence should be considered when making treatment decisions: the demeanor of the calf, its milk consumption, its dehydration rate, the presence of acidosis, and the detection of signs indicative of bacteremia and endotoxemia. Indications of such signs include the presence of fever or hypothermia, reduced milk consumption, depression and scleral vessels injection. According to the proposed guidelines, the provision of milk should be maintained at its current quantity and there should be no reduction in its offer. Calves that are bright and alert, consuming the offered milk in its entirety and exhibiting a dehydration rate of less than 7% should be administered oral electrolyte solutions. Calves that have 8% or higher dehydration rate and/or are weak or have weak or absent suckling reflex necessitate treatment with intravenous fluids, followed by oral electrolyte solutions and subsequent reevaluation. Calves with any combination of the following signs indicative of bacteremia-endotoxemia, obvious bilateral scleral vessels injection, fever or hypothermia, depression and significant reduction in milk consumption of more than 50%, should be treated with a combination of antibacterials and non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and should be given intravenous fluids. In cases of fever without any other indication of bacteremia and with a decrease in milk consumption of less than 25%, oral electrolyte solutions and NSAIDs without antibacterials should be administered and the calf should be monitored for fever and further signs of bacteremia – endotoxemia the next day. In calves with blood or mucosal shreds in feces, the administration of antibacterials without NSAIDs is recommended. The proposed guidelines are designed to ensure the timely detection and treatment of bacteremia-endotoxemia, with a focus on the judicious use of antibacterials. Furthermore, their application has been demonstrated that effectively corrects dehydration, electrolyte imbalances, and acidosis, thereby enhancing the viability of the calves.

Keywords: diarrhea syndrome, neonatal calves, treatment, antimicrobials, guideline

MASTITIS IN DAIRY COWS, RISK FACTORS AND CONTROL MEASURES

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Mastitis represents one of the most significant health disorders in the udders of dairy cows. They cause significant direct and indirect losses. In relation to the intensity of the changes that are present, mastitis can be subclinical and clinical. Clinical forms of mastitis are accompanied by clear changes in the tissue and secretion of the mammary gland and changes in the general condition of the animal, while in subclinical forms the changes relate to the composition and amount of secretion of the mammary gland. The frequency of occurrence of mastitis is affected by the effect of risk factors, such as factors related to the animal itself and those related to housing conditions and handling of the animal, especially during milking. Most important are those factors related to animal including age and phase of lactation. Control measures are aimed at reducing the negative impact of risk factors and eliminating already existing infections.

Key words: mastitis, risk factors, control measures

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No: 451-03-137/2025-03/200117).

EVALUATING DRINKING WATER QUALITY, BIOFILMS AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE GENES IN BIOFILMS AFTER A ONE-TIME CLEANING AND DISINFECTION OF A DRINKING WATER SYSTEM IN WEAN-TO-FINISH SWINE BARNs

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Biofilms in drinking water systems and poor drinking water quality in swine farms present challenges in maintaining biosecurity, it also may impact drinking water treatment, and potentially restrict the amount of drinking water that is available to the pigs. There are solutions available to improve drinking water quality, to remove mineral build up and biofilms in drinking water systems. However, there is a lack of knowledge on how drinking water systems and the biology of drinking water lines can impact the pigs related to health status, production performance, water medications, and antimicrobial stewardship. Our objectives were to evaluate the impacts of a onetime cleaning and disinfection protocol at sanitary stop with a peracetic acid (PAA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) based product on biofilms and the biofilm regrowth rate, drinking water quality and genetic presence and phenotypic expression of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). Six wean-to-finish barns with 2400 pigs in each barn (14 4000 pigs in total) in the Midwestern United States were enrolled into this longitudinal study. The wean-to-finish barns had well water as drinking water source. Drinking Water and drinking water line samples were collected aseptically pre-treatment (0), after drinking water lines were cleaned and disinfected with the PAA/H₂O₂ based product during 24 hours contact time (1), and 3, 5, 7, 14, 21, 42, 56, 77 days post-treatment. The quantities of biofilm were assessed via standard plate counts. Drinking water quality was assessed for minerals, coliforms and *E. coli* content. Metagenomics were utilized to define antimicrobial resistance genes and phenotypic resistance was assessed from drinking water line samples through drug-infused blood agar plates containing chlortetracycline (CTC) or lincomycin, as two major drugs used in the swine industry. Preliminary water results demonstrate that drinking water samples from compartments had higher average coliform counts than those present from drinking water samples at the source (well water). The quantities of biofilm from drinking water line samples ranged from 0 colony forming units (CFUs)/mL to 3.3 billion CFU's/mL and showed differences between compartments at some pig sites. A hemolytic F18 *Escherichia coli* with EAST1 toxin and PAA genes, *Staphylococcus hyicus*, opportunistic pig pathogens, and normal flora grew on CTC or lincomycin drug-infused plates, or on both CTC and lincomycin drug-infused plates. This research study shows that swine drinking water systems and biofilms contribute to drinking water quality challenges and can act as a potential reservoir for pathogens and ARGs in the swine industry.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance genes, drinking water quality, biofilms, water lines, disinfection

INTERPRETATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY TESTING WHEN CLINICAL BREAKPOINTS ARE NOT AVAILABLE

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Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) is a cornerstone of evidence-based antimicrobial therapy in veterinary medicine and guides clinicians in the selection of effective treatments for bacterial infections. However, interpretation of AST results is often challenging due to the limited availability of clinical breakpoints specific to veterinary pathogens and host species. In the absence of established clinical breakpoints, alternative approaches to interpretation are essential to ensure responsible use of antimicrobials and to combat antimicrobial resistance. AST methods commonly used in veterinary microbiology include broth microdilution, agar dilution and disk diffusion. Broth microdilution is widely recognised as the reference method for the determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and provides reproducible and quantitative results. Although agar dilution is less commonly used due to its high workload, it is still a standardised method with high accuracy. Disk diffusion, on the other hand, offers a simpler and more cost-effective qualitative method to classify isolates as susceptible (S - susceptible, standard dosing regimen), intermediate (I - susceptible, increased exposure) or resistant (R) based on the diameter of the inhibition zones. Regardless of the method used, careful interpretation is critical when clinical breakpoints are not available. In such situations, the use of epidemiological cut-off values (ECOFF) is of central importance. ECOFFs distinguish wild-type bacterial populations (i.e. those without acquired or mutated resistance mechanisms) from non-wild-type populations. They do not predict clinical outcomes but serve as an important tool for resistance surveillance and targeting empirical therapy when there are no clinical breakpoints. The European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) plays a key role in establishing and updating ECOFFs, supported by data from international collaborative studies. For veterinary applications, the EUCAST subcommittee VETCAST provides specific recommendations tailored to animal pathogens, considering the unique pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters relevant to veterinary species. In situations where there are no species-specific veterinary breakpoints, the VETCAST and EUCAST guidelines recommend a cautious, informed approach to the interpretation of AST results. This may include the incorporation of ECOFF data, knowledge of drug pharmacology, clinical experience and pathogen-specific information. For certain combinations of animal pathogens and antimicrobials, VETCAST has begun to develop specific clinical breakpoints, but there are still gaps, particularly for less common species or for drugs that are not routinely used in human medicine. In conclusion, when clinical breakpoints are not available in veterinary medicine, AST interpretation is based on a combination of standardised test methods and alternative interpretation criteria such as ECOFF. EUCAST and VETCAST provide an important framework to ensure consistency and scientific rigour in this process. Continued efforts in surveillance, data sharing and the establishment of veterinary-specific clinical breakpoints are critical to optimising antimicrobial stewardship in veterinary medicine and addressing the global challenge of antimicrobial resistance.

Key words: antimicrobial susceptibility testing; clinical breakpoints; epidemiological cut-off values

PHARMACOVIGILANCE AND THE FUTURE OF ANTIBACTERIAL SAFETY

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Antibiotics (AB) are one of the greatest achievements of modern medicine, but their widespread use has led to unprecedented challenges in terms of drug safety and antimicrobial resistance (AMR). This presentation will explore the evolving role of pharmacovigilance in the protection of antibacterial therapies. It will examine the current challenges in detecting and managing adverse effects of antibiotics, the complexity of resistance surveillance, and the strategic integration of pharmacovigilance into antimicrobial stewardship programs (AMS). Looking to the future, it will discuss how innovations such as big data analytics, artificial intelligence and global surveillance networks will change the future of antibacterial safety. Case studies and real-world examples will provide insights into how pharmacovigilance needs to adapt to ensure the effective, safe and sustainable use of antibiotics in a rapidly changing healthcare landscape. The AWaRE (Access, Watch, and Reserve) classification was created by the World Health Organization (WHO) to support antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) initiatives and facilitate data collection and comparison for monitoring AB consumption. The influence of different drugs and antibiotic classes on antimicrobial resistance serves as the basis for this classification. The WHO's goal is that 60% of the AB taken in a country should come from people who are considered less at risk of AMR (the Access group). The WHO guideline for an integrated local AMS policy is based on five pillars: strengthening infection control through water, sanitation and hygiene initiatives; ensuring access to regulation of antimicrobials; improving awareness, education and training; developing national coordination; and surveillance, monitoring and evaluation. The use of pharmacovigilance (PV) data to report suspected cases of antimicrobial resistance, treatment failure and inappropriate or off-label use of Abs has been proposed as a useful and cost-effective approach to challenging situations. The basis of PV is signal detection, which can lead to changes in the approval status or even the withdrawal of medicinal products in the event of adverse drug reactions (ADRs). One example of this is labeling changes to restrict the use of fluoroquinolones. PV has contributed to almost 40% of antibiotics introduced between 1980 and 2009 being withdrawn from the market due to safety concerns or ineffectiveness compared to other drugs.

Key words: antimicrobial resistance; antibacterial safety; pharmacovigilance; antimicrobial stewardship programs

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND PLANETARY HEALTH: A GLOBAL CHALLENGE FOR SAFE USE OF ANTIBIOTICS

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Antibiotic resistance (AMR) represents one of the most urgent global health threats of our time, with far-reaching consequences not only for human and animal health but also for planetary health as a whole. The overuse and misuse of antibiotics across sectors—including human medicine, veterinary practice, agriculture, and food production—have accelerated the development and spread of resistant microorganisms. This undermines the effectiveness of life-saving treatments and threatens to reverse decades of medical progress. AMR is a natural phenomenon, but its rapid acceleration is largely driven by human activity. In many parts of the world, antibiotics are used unnecessarily—for viral infections, for disease prevention in healthy animals, and even to promote growth in livestock. The consequence is the emergence of resistant strains of bacteria that can spread across populations and borders through travel, trade, food systems, and environmental contamination. Water, soil, and wastewater are now recognized as critical pathways for the spread of resistance genes, particularly when antibiotic residues and resistant organisms are released into ecosystems without proper treatment. The discovery of new antibiotics has slowed dramatically in recent decades, with few novel classes introduced since the 1980s. At the same time, resistance to existing antibiotics continues to rise, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where access to clean water, sanitation, and healthcare is often limited, and where antibiotics may be available over the counter without prescription or quality control. The World Health Organization, along with many scientific bodies, has warned that we may be entering a post-antibiotic era, in which common infections and routine surgeries once again carry high risks of complications and mortality. This challenge must be addressed through a Planetary Health approach that recognizes the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health as well as the health of our planet. Responsible prescribing practices, improved diagnostics, enhanced infection prevention and control, reduced use of antibiotics in agriculture, and better wastewater treatment are all essential components of a coordinated global response. Equally important is public and professional education about the drivers of AMR and the urgent need to conserve existing antibiotics as a shared resource. Ultimately, the fight against antibiotic resistance is not just a biomedical issue—it is a planetary health issue. Preserving antibiotic effectiveness is essential for sustainable development, food security, health equity, and the resilience of health systems worldwide.

Key words: resistance, antibiotics, planet, health

PROBIOTIC USE AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: MARKET OVERVIEW AND PRELIMINARY SCREENING

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The use of probiotics is steadily increasing, with these products commonly marketed as dietary supplements and, in some cases, as medicinal products. This study provides a brief overview of probiotics currently available on the Serbian market and investigates antibiotic resistance in five food supplements and one medicinal product. Market analysis of probiotic products in Serbia revealed significant variability in colony-forming unit (CFU) counts and a wide range of health claims, some of which are medicinal claims. Lactobacilli were the most frequently identified microorganisms, commonly found in products sold both in pharmacies and online. Experimental findings confirmed the presence of antibiotic-resistant strains among various *Lactobacillus* species in these products. While probiotics offer health benefits, their potential role in spreading antibiotic resistance must not be overlooked. Therefore, regulatory frameworks should be updated to mandate antimicrobial resistance (AMR) screening for probiotic products, accompanied by clear guidelines for their safe use and disposal.

Key words: probiotic; antibiotic resistance; market analysis; antibiotic resistance screening; dietary supplements; *Lactobacillus*

ANTIBACTERIAL USE IN NUMBERS

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Antibacterials are essential medicines but their effectiveness is jeopardized by the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Antibiotic use is one of the changable factors to reverse AMR. With the application of drug utilisation studies and conducting surveillance activities, we are able to identify the problematic areas of antibiotic use and afterwards develop tailored strategies to rationalise antibacterial use. In this lecture we aimed to give insight into antibacterial use surveillance worldwide and in Europe. We will mainly use the publicly available reports of different organisation (WHO GLASS, ECDC ESAC-Net) or the online WHO GLASS dashboard. If time allows would like also to refer to the point-prevalence survey conducted in acute care hospitals in the EU region. We aim to show the level and in the pattern of antibacterial use globally and in the EU. Presented data will be primarily expressed in WHO recommended metrics: DDD/1000 inhabitants/day. In conclusion, we will reveal the huge disparities in the scale and in the pattern of antibacterial use worldwide and in Europe. The suboptimal quality of antibiotic use including the lack of achieving the WHO defined target of Access antibiotic use in many countries will be presented. The dominance of broad spectra antibiotics will be highlighted, with some exceptional and exemplary Nordic countries with strong antibiotic policy.

Key words: antibiotic utilisation, quality indicators, scale of use, pattern of use

Acknowledgment: This work has been implemented with support provided by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology of Hungary from the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund, financed by ITM NKFIA TKP2021-EGA-32.

NARROW TREATMENT STRATEGIES FOR PEDIATRIC SYSTEMIC GRAM-NEGATIVE INFECTIONS: INSIGHTS FROM A CASE SERIES

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Systemic Gram-negative infections in pediatric patients represent a serious clinical concern due to their rapid progression and high morbidity and mortality rates. Gram-negative bacteria such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter hormaechei* and *Burkholderia cepacia* are common pathogens in these infections, particularly in neonates and immunocompromised children. These bacteria trigger a potent immune response that can lead to sepsis and septic shock. These infections pose a significant risk in pediatric surgical critical care units. In neonates risk factors include prematurity, low birth weight, invasive procedures, congenital malformations of the gastrointestinal tract and prolonged hospitalization. In older children, systemic infections may arise from gastrointestinal sources, as a consequence of trauma or related to ventilator associated pneumonia. Clinical manifestations can be nonspecific and prompt diagnosis and treatment are critical. Blood cultures remain the gold standard for pathogen identification. Antimicrobial resistance, particularly the rise of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing organisms and carbapenem-resistant strains, complicates management and underscores the need for antibiotic stewardship. This case series analyzes four critically ill pediatric patients with systemic Gram-negative infections, providing a detailed examination of the therapeutic challenges encountered and the corresponding treatment outcomes.

Case 1. An infant with a congenital spina bifida malformation developed a severe central nervous system infection caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* resistant to all available systemic therapies. Due to limited intravenous treatment options, intrathecal colistin was administered for 21 days. While the therapy successfully eradicated the bacterial infection, it was associated with serious side effects.

Case 2. A newborn with a congenital gastrointestinal malformation developed sepsis caused by *Enterobacter hormaechei*, leading to severe multi-organ dysfunction.

Case 3. A young child developed an infection with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* involving a cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) drainage system. The infection resulted in a prolonged, one-month stay in the intensive care unit, requiring external CSF drainage and mechanical ventilation.

Case 4. A child hospitalized for corrective spinal surgery acquired an infection with *Burkholderia cepacia* during the hospital stay. Treatment options were extremely limited due to the pathogen's resistance profile.

Key words: children, Gram negative bacteria, Systemic infections

NANOANTIBIOTICS AS A STRATEGY IN THE FIGHT AGAINST ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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It is well known that antimicrobial resistance is a major public health problem, as well as the lack of newly discovered molecules with antimicrobial properties. Pharmaceutical technology offers various strategies that could potentially be applied to increase the efficacy of both newly discovered and existing antibiotics. Nanomaterials are defined as particles with at least one dimension smaller than 100 nm, and as the particles are reduced in size, there is a complete change in their physicochemical, biopharmaceutical, and clinical effects. The aim of this paper was to provide a review of the scientific literature in the field of nanoantibiotics. A literature search was conducted in PubMed using the keywords and their combinations: nanoantibiotics, nanotechnology, and antimicrobial resistance. Nanoantibiotics are defined as antibiotic particles with nanodimensions, or as antibiotics encapsulated in nanocarriers. Apart from their antibiotic effect on Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, numerous studies have demonstrated the potential of nanocarrier systems to enhance antifungal and antiviral effects. One of the reasons for the increased efficiency and reduced side effects of nanoantibiotics is their targeted delivery to the target tissues. Although the mechanisms of action of nanoantibiotics are not fully understood, it is believed that they pass through the bacterial cell wall, interact with bacterial cellular structures, and alter the bacteria's metabolism in a different way than conventional antibiotics. In this way, the development of resistance to nanoantibiotics is made more difficult for bacteria. Non-biological adverse effects, physical disruption and of bacterial structure and Trojan horse strategy are some of the mechanisms that make nanomaterials more effective. Based on the reviewed literature, it can be concluded that nanoantibiotics have great potential for further research and application, and represent an encouraging concept in the fight against antimicrobial resistance.

Key words: Nanoparticles, Nanotechnology, Nanomaterials, Antimicrobial agents

Acknowledgments: This research is supported by the project funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (451-03-136/2025-03/200114).

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE – MULTI-RESISTANT INFECTIONS IN COMPANION ANIMAL PRACTICE

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major threat to human, animal, and environmental health, and is expected to evolve as the main cause of death in humans by 2050 if not successfully contained. To reduce the development and spread of AMR, and therefore preserve the efficacy of antimicrobials for the treatment of infections, it is necessary to optimize the use of these drugs across all One Health sectors, including veterinary medicine. Antimicrobial stewardship in the veterinary field is not only important for the benefit of animal health but is also inevitable for reducing the risk of AMR in humans, considering the growing evidence about resistance transmission on the human-animal-environment interface. This presentation describes the latest scientific findings and evidence-based best practices related to prudent use of antimicrobials in infections of companion animals commonly caused by multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria. It covers the treatment of skin infections caused by staphylococci, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and *S. pseudintermedius* (MRSP); otitis externa caused by staphylococci, streptococci and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; and urinary tract infections caused by MDR *Escherichia coli*. The aspects described include the most common resistance patterns; recommendations for first- and second-line antimicrobial drug choices and their dosages; preferred local or systemic administration routes for specific infections. Special emphasis is put on the categorization of antimicrobial classes and recommendations related to their use in veterinary medicine according to the European Medicines Agency’s (EMA) Antimicrobial Advice Ad Hoc Expert Group (AMEG). Following the recommendations outlined in this presentation can ensure safe and effective antimicrobial therapy in companion animals when encountering MDR infections. The optimized use of antimicrobials in such clinical situations reduces the risk of resistance development and therefore helps preserving the long-term efficacy of antimicrobials for the sake of human, animal and environmental health.

Key words: antimicrobial use, antimicrobial resistance, multidrug-resistance, companion animals, dermatitis, otitis externa, urinary tract infections

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PATTERNS IN STAPHYLOCOCCI FROM CANINE CLINICAL SAMPLES IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Staphylococcus* spp. from companion animals represents a significant challenge to veterinary medicine and public health. This study investigated the phenotypic resistance profiles and genetic determinants of AMR in Staphylococci from canine clinical samples in North Macedonia. A total of 170 Staphylococci were analyzed, comprising *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* (90%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (7.6%), and other staphylococcal species (2.4%). Species identification was performed using MALDI-TOF MS, while antimicrobial susceptibility was determined via disk diffusion against 12 antibiotics from eight classes using CLSI guideline VETO1S-Ed6. Molecular detection of methicillin resistance was conducted using conventional PCR targeting *mecA* and *mecC* genes. High resistance rates were observed for penicillin G (73%), tetracycline (70%), erythromycin (62.3%), and clindamycin (61.8%). Multidrug resistance (MDR), defined as resistance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial classes, was detected in 70.5% of isolates. Methicillin resistance was confirmed in 28.8% of isolates through *mecA* detection. The *mecC* gene was not detected in any isolate. Resistance to critically important antimicrobials was concerning, with resistance rates of 32.3% for enrofloxacin, 31.2% for marbofloxacin, and 22.3% for pradofloxacin. Analysis of resistance profiles revealed 68 unique patterns, with the most common profile including resistance to oxacillin, penicillin G, tetracycline, erythromycin, clindamycin, gentamicin, enrofloxacin, marbofloxacin, pradofloxacin, and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. This study provides the first comprehensive characterization of AMR in canine staphylococcal isolates in North Macedonia, revealing high prevalence of MDR and methicillin resistance. These findings highlight the urgent need for implementing antimicrobial stewardship programs to guide effective therapeutic strategies for companion animals.

Keywords: *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*, methicillin resistance, multidrug resistance

SURGICAL SITE INFECTIONS (SSI) AND ANTIBIOTICS USAGE

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Surgical site infections (SSI) are mostly associated with particular surgical procedures and the facility in which those procedures were performed. According to this definition, a surgical procedure is defined as a procedure in which at least one incision is made through the skin or mucous membrane or surgery is performed via an incision made during a previous surgical procedure. SSI accounts for about a quarter of hospital infections and is the most common source of infections in surgical patients. The development of SSI is the result of complex interaction between microbes and the host as well as the surgical factors. The sources of bacterial contamination in surgical wounds can be classified as endogenous and exogenous sources. The endogenous sources of contamination come from the patient's own skin, remote skin and organ infections and are also related to the surgical class. The exogenous sources of contamination originate from the surgical team, the environment, and the materials and instruments used. The type of procedure, the surgical environment, surgical expertise and post operative care all contain risk factors for the development of SSI. Various endocrinopathies significantly increase the risk of SSI in veterinary medicine, and anesthesia and/or surgical duration are among the most frequently discussed risks for SSI. Although there are numerous risk factors for the occurrence of SSI, few factors are considered to be the most crucial for SSI prevention in veterinary medicine:

- Considering hand hygiene is regarded by the World Health Organization as the key factor in the prevention of healthcare-associated infections (simple, cheap, and efficient method).
- Considering animal health care workers, above the risk of transmitting disease from one patient to another also have the potential to transmit zoonosis to themselves and their community.

From a causal and consequential perspective, SSI are related with increased financial costs due to additional surgical treatments, antibiotics usage, hospital stay, emotional distress for owners, and drastically affect the animal's welfare. Also, SSI can lead to excess death because of complications. According to everything mentioned before, "better safe than sorry" is logical conclusion about SSI, especially in today's antibiotics era, when excessive and irrational use of antibiotics leads to antimicrobial resistance.

Key words: surgery, SSI, risks prevention

MICROBIOME, NEONATES AND RESISTANCE: CHALLENGES IN VETERINARY NEONATOLOGY

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The gut microbiome is one of the key factors in developing of immune, metabolic, and neural homeostasis, and its formation begins during intrauterine life. In the context of veterinary neonatology, special attention is given to puppies, whose microbiome is significantly influenced by the maternal microbial status, the mode of delivery, and early postnatal interventions. Excessive and often unjustified use of antibiotics in pregnant bitches, especially in the absence of clear indications, can have far-reaching consequences – not only for the dam but also for the offspring – by altering the microbiome and increasing the risk of developing antimicrobial resistance. According to Barker's hypothesis of fetal programming, intrauterine conditions profoundly impact on health in adulthood. This opens up the possibility that antibiotic therapy during pregnancy may act as a programming factor, predisposing puppies to metabolic and immunological imbalances, as well as early colonization by resistant bacteria. Early and targeted interventions in neonatology enable the reduction of empirical antibiotic use and allow for the timely recognition of neonatal infections. Additionally, the use of probiotics is increasingly being recognized as a more effective and safer strategy for modulating gut microbiota, both therapeutically and preventively. Probiotics may help restore eubiosis in puppies, especially those born by cesarean section or exposed to early antimicrobial treatments. Integrating knowledge on early microbiome development and the influence of environmental factors on epigenetic mechanisms provides a foundation for shaping sustainable strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance and improve neonatal health in veterinary medicine.

Key words: microbiome, fetal programming, antimicrobial resistance, neonatology, puppies, antibiotics, probiotics

SELECTED ESSENTIAL OILS EFFECT AGAINST *STREPTOCOCCUS CANIS* ISOLATED FROM BITCH VAGINAL SWAB

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Since ancient times it has been known that essential oils from many plants exhibit antimicrobial activity against a wide range of microorganisms. The use of essential oils with bactericidal and/or bacteriostatic effects in human medicine is widespread, especially as supportive therapy for antibiotic treatments. In veterinary medicine, such (alternative) ways of treating certain bacterial infections are still in their infancy. *Streptococcus canis* stands out as one of the most common causes of clinical (and subclinical) vaginitis in bitches. Isolated *Streptococcus canis* from the vagina of a bitch was subjected to testing of the antimicrobial effect of nine essential oils (tea tree, sage, thyme, carrot, palmarosa, yarrow, marjoram, camphor and German chamomile). Two-fold dilutions of essential oils were made at percentages of 1%, 2%, 4% and 8% in cold-pressed tamanu oil as a diluent. Cold pressed oil from tamanu nut did not show antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus canis*. The microdilution method was used, where double dilutions were used. The lowest concentration of essential oils in which there was no growth of bacteria was considered inhibitory for its growth. Of all the essential oils listed, only tea tree oil did not show an antimicrobial effect at any percentage concentration, while all other oils exhibited antimicrobial activity, even at the lowest tested concentration. Findings from such research in the field of veterinary medicine certainly pave the way for the use of essential oils for the prevention or treatment of potential bacterial infections of the vagina of bitches, all with the aim of reducing antimicrobial resistance and the use of antibiotics for this purpose.

Key words: essential oil, *Streptococcus canis*, vagina, bitch, antimicrobial resistance

Acknowledgment: This work/study/research/report... was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

This study was funded by the Scientific Veterinary Institute „Novi Sad“, under the Proof of Concept Program (“Development of preparation of a combination of essential oils with antimicrobial action against the most common vaginal infections in bitches.”), through the financial support of the Serbia Accelerating Innovation and Entrepreneurship (SAIGE) Project, a joint investment by the Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, the World Bank and the European Union.

CONJUNCTIVITIS: WHAT ARE WE TREATING AND WHAT ARE WE CAUSING?

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Conjunctivitis is one of the most common ophthalmological diseases in small animal practice characterized with conjunctival redness and discharge. Complications of this condition can lead to vision loss. Conjunctival redness and ocular discharge are not exclusive only to conjunctivitis, but they can also be observed in other ophthalmological conditions such as glaucoma and uveitis. One of the most common bacterial isolates from conjunctiva that can cause this type of clinical signs is *Staphylococcus* spp., usually found on the skin surface of dogs. These bacteria can cause skin and ear canal infections or infections on the ocular surface. The presence of bacteria in ocular cultures is similar in healthy patients and those with conjunctivitis. In cats with conjunctivitis, bacteria are detected at lower rate than in dogs. Common bacterial isolates include *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Micrococaceae*, *Pseudomonas* and occasionally *Corynebacterium*. These bacteria can also be found in healthy cats, but their presence does not significantly increase in conjunctivitis cases, likely due to natural host resistance to local bacterial ocular infections. However, they can coexist or cause secondary infections in cases of feline herpes virus, Chlamydia or Mycoplasma infections. The aim of the study was to determine the frequency of antibiotic use, the duration of clinical signs, and the indication for their use in ophthalmic patients admitted in the first quarter of 2025 at Veterinary Teaching Hospital of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine University of Zagreb. During that period 37.4 % of 115 dogs and cats admitted for ophthalmological examination had previously received topical antibiotics for various conditions, among which keratoconjunctivitis sicca was the most frequent, observed in 25 % of cases. None of the admitted patients had undergone a prior bacteriological examination. In 30.23 % of cases clinical signs lasted longer than two weeks. Tobramycin was prescribed in 60 % of cases following neomycin sulfate and polymyxin B sulfate in addition with dexamethasone in 27.5 %. In patients previously treated with topical antibiotics, a bacteriological examination of the ocular surface was performed in only two dogs with infected corneal ulcers, in which no bacteria were isolated. In conclusion, the use of topical antibiotics can impair the isolation of bacteria in cases of canine keratitis, further emphasizing the importance of targeted microbiological testing before initiating empirical therapy. Thorough ophthalmological examination with bacteriological sampling is essential for appropriate treatment and preventing antimicrobial resistance in all cases of long term presence of conjunctival symptoms.

Key words: conjunctivitis, ophthalmological examination, antibacterial resistance, dog, cat

WILDLIFE, ECOSYSTEMS, AND DISEASE TRANSMISSION: IMPLICATIONS FOR ONE HEALTH AND ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARDSHIP

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While antibiotic use in livestock production has steadily declined in the United States of America since 2015, antibiotics are still commonly used to prevent, treat, and control bacterial infections. Good antimicrobial stewardship for herd management strives to reduce antibiotic use and understand the landscape of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The University of Florida Cervidae Health Research Initiative (CHeRI) aims reduce antibiotic use in farmed deer with the following objectives: 1) conduct passive surveillance to understand which bacterial species most commonly infect farmed deer, 2) survey deer farmers to understand which are the most commonly used antibiotics, 3) characterize resistance profiles of the two most common bacteria involved in morbidity and mortality of deer, 4) provide recommendations to deer farmers about good antibiotic use and stewardship. We conducted necropsies on 902 dead farmed white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*) from 72 deer farms in Florida during 2016-2023 to assess cause of death. We collected biological samples from lung, spleen, heart, kidney and liver and conducted aerobic and anaerobic bacterial culture. For a subset of these samples that were positive for the most common bacterial infection, *Escherichia coli* (n=60), we conducted antimicrobial susceptibility testing for 13 antimicrobials commonly used on deer farms or of veterinary or medical importance. We found that in aerobic conditions 30% of the *E. coli* isolates were resistant to at least one antibiotic, while 68% were resistant under anaerobic conditions. The highest levels of resistance were found for antibiotics in the tetracycline family under aerobic conditions and under anaerobic conditions antibiotics in the aminoglycosides had the highest resistance. For a subset of animals that were positive for the second most common agent of bacterial infection, *Trueperella pyogenes* (n=37), we tested susceptibility for 9 commonly used antibiotics under aerobic conditions. Similar to *E. coli*, *T. pyogenes* had the highest resistance to tetracyclines and aminoglycosides. For each bacterial species we whole genome sequenced isolates from each sample to assess the presence of resistance genes and to compare the phenotype of resistance vs. the genotype of resistance. For *E. coli*, ceftiofur, florfenicol, and enrofloxacin had low genotype-phenotype agreement whereas tetracycline, oxytetracycline, and ampicillin were the antimicrobials with high resistance rates and strong genotype-phenotype agreement. Both *E. coli* and *T. pyogenes* are commonly associated with pneumonia which is a common cause of death in farmed white-tailed deer. Both bacterial species presented high levels of resistance to tetracyclines and aminoglycosides and had genes that coincided with resistance to these antimicrobials. We recommend that deer farmers cease to use these families of antibiotics for treatment of infections, or any other aspect of herd management. Agricultural Extension services will focus on conveying best practices for antimicrobial use including profiles of effective antibiotics for use in farmed deer.

Keywords: Antibiotic use; deer farming; *Odocoileus virginianus*; Resistome

Acknowledgements: This work is part of the Ph.D. dissertation of An-Chi Cheng and the M.Sc. thesis of Austin Surplis. We thank all of the deer farmers who contributed specimens to the UF CHeRI Diagnostic Testing Laboratory.

INNOVATIONS IN PROBIOTIC FORMULATION: TECHNOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES FOR REDUCING AMR RISKS

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) stands as one of the most critical global health challenges of the 21st century, posing a serious threat that could reverse decades of medical advancement. Therefore, a multi-sectoral, globally coordinated effort is essential to address its root causes, mitigate the impact, and preserve the effectiveness of antimicrobials for future generations. One of the most promising solutions lies in the application of microbial probiotic strains, offering a safe, natural, and complementary approach to combat antimicrobial resistance. Although they are not a substitute for antibiotics, probiotics play a valuable role in a comprehensive AMR strategy by helping to prevent infections, reduce the need for antibiotics, and suppress resistant pathogens, particularly from the standpoint of preventive medicine and maintaining a healthy microbiome. The notable attention of the scientific and wider community given to probiotics as key players in the AMR fight can be explained by their ability to exhibit multi-antimicrobial mechanisms of action, including health-promoting and immunomodulatory capacities. For many years, strains of the *Bacillus* genus have attracted significant interest in fundamental research and have also been recognised as valuable tools in industrial applications due to their adaptability and wide range of functional properties. The *Bacillus* strains are commonly employed as producing microorganisms in enzyme production, with wide application in food processing and the detergent industry. They are important actors in the field of bioremediation and waste management, due to ability to degrade the organic compounds, resulting in environmental decontamination and waste decomposition. *Bacillus* strains are well-known in the agricultural sector as powerful biocontrol agents and biostimulants, enabling plant growth promotion, enhancing nutrient availability, inducing plant resistance and protection against phytopathogens. Members of the *Bacillus* genus exhibit favourable characteristics, speaking of the possible application in the field of the pharmaceutical industry, as probiotics in food and feed supplements. Among conventionally used probiotic isolates, those selected from the genus *Bacillus* have more evident advantages, as spore-forming strains, including rapid germination and multiplication, and endurance towards a multitude of severe environmental conditions, providing a wide range of health benefits to the host. Additionally, they are characterized as producers of antagonistic compounds effective against a wide range of pathogens, but also extracellular digestive enzymes enhancing feed digestibility and nutrient absorption. *Bacillus* strains have demonstrated the ability to enhance both cellular and humoral immune responses by increasing the number of isolated lymphoid follicles in the intestinal mucosa, regulating the development of gut-associated lymphoid tissue, stimulating antibody production and boosting macrophage activity. Although most research on probiotics has focused on their indisputable beneficial aspects, there is a necessity to raise awareness and questions on the hidden obstacle in terms of their application safety, regarding potential antibiotic resistance and concern over the antibiotic resistance genes transfer. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has established clear guidelines and safety criteria for the use of *Bacillus* species as probiotics in the food and feed chain, pointing out the importance of preliminary screening and bacterial strains characterization concerning identification of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes in their genomes. Key regulation points address the absence of acquired antimicrobial resistance genes, the necessity for whole genome sequencing, qualification for the Qualified Presumption of Safety (QPS) List and phenotypic antibiotic susceptibility testing. The preliminary results from our research group related to the molecular screening of newly isolated *Bacillus* strains

have shown varying distribution of AMR genes in the investigated population, with a small number of strains exhibiting the complete absence of the investigated genes. This molecular approach as the first large-scale screening step thus enables preliminary selection of the AMR determinants-free strains, suitable for moving forward with the next stages of characterization, as required by regulatory guidelines, with the goal of bringing a novel and safe probiotic strain suitable for potential commercial use.

Key words: AMR, *Bacillus*, probiotic, mechanism of action, microbiome, EFSA

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the programs 451-03-136/2025-03/200134 and 451-03-137/2025-03/200134 of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovations of the Republic of Serbia.

THE PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF SURVEY ABOUT BIOSECURITY MEASURES ON SELECTED RAINBOW TROUT FARMS IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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The intensification of aquaculture and the globalization of trade in aquatic products have led to the emergence and re-emergence of infectious diseases representing a significant economic and environmental challenge to society. The old adage that “prevention is better than cure” certainly applies to aquaculture diseases, particularly when the economic impacts of disease outbreaks have proven to be huge and biosecurity practices can prevent these. Generally, OIE (WOAH) defines Biosecurity in aquaculture as a set of management and physical measures designed to reduce the risk of introduction, establishment and spread of pathogenic agents to, from and within an aquatic animal population. There are not many literature sources on aquaculture production and fish health monitoring in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Based on the actual official data from the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the total production of Rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) fish farms in 2023 was 3.766,6 tons, based on the facilities of the surface 110.997,0 m². To the best of the author's knowledge, no prior research has surveyed biosecurity measures in rainbow trout farms in Bosnia and Herzegovina. It was a reason to arrange screening investigations to check which staff knowledge and implementation of biosecurity principles are present on seven rainbow trout fish farms. Our research assessed aquaculture production in the following municipalities: Ribnik, Šipovo (two farms each) and Jezero, Kneževo, Trebinje (one farm each). The fish farms included in the study had production ranging from four tons of fish per year to more than 500 tons, with a total production of more than 1.700 tons. The study included a survey with fish farm production managers and the use of a questionnaire with 15 questions of important parameters i.e. the written biosecurity plan, cleaning and sanitation protocol and disinfection protocol. Additionally, there were issues like the application of concrete biosecurity measures, practices that minimize the risk of introducing and spreading infectious diseases (incl. zoonoses) as well as preventive measures for improvement of fish health generally. Interestingly, in all visited fish farms there has been a decrease in water supply for normal maintenance of fish production in the previous ten years, which would be the direct consequence of climate change. Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that in most fish farms with small production (up to 100 tons per year), knowledge and realization of the basic principles of biosecurity measures are at a low level and that there is big space for improvement of the current status. This primarily relates to continuous education and raising awareness about the importance of assessment of biosecurity measures including the design of specific protocols for each farm. Future data collection on the implementation of biosecurity measures, including expanding the research to a larger number of fish farms, would provide a more detailed insight into the state of strengths and weaknesses of fish production in this country.

Key words: Disease prevention, salmonidae production, Balkan

Acknowledgments: This publication is based upon work from COST Action BIOAQUA, CA22160, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) and funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological development of Serbia (The Contract No. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117 of 4.2.2025.)

ANTIFUNGAL RESISTANCE IN PLANT PROTECTION AND RESTORATION OF WILD TYPE SENSITIVITY

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Fungicide resistance in plant pathogenic fungi poses a significant threat to plant protection, leading to reduced efficacy of fungicides. This resistance arises from the selection of resistant individuals within pathogen populations under high fungicide pressure. Repeated application of single-mode-of-action fungicides on large populations of polycyclic pathogens in favorable conditions significantly contributes to this selection process. While the wild-type pathogen populations are typically sensitive, fungicide pressure shifts the population sensitivity towards resistance. To mitigate this, alternating fungicides with different modes of action is a common strategy, however, limited availability of such fungicides for certain diseases, restricts control options. Further, the EU is intensively working on removal of toxic active substances which is in alignment with one of its ambitions, that by 2030, the use of more hazardous pesticides in the EU should be reduced by 50%. Therefore, new solutions should be implemented, hence the aim of this abstract is to investigate the effects of microbial biocontrol measures on restoring the wild type sensitivity. Research indicates that resistant pathogen populations often exhibit lower fitness compared to wild-type individuals. Consequently, integrating microorganism-based fungicides into plant protection plans can improve the phyllosphere microbiome and restore the prevalence of wild-type pathogens, offering a potential solution to resistance. Three relevant studies proved that beneficial microorganisms affect the balance towards wild type pathogen population by all known modes of action: competition, induced resistance, mycoparasitism and antibiosis. Also, the use of beneficial organisms in plant protection programmes proved to reduce the use of chemical pesticides by 25%, which decreased the impact of chemical pesticides on selection of pathogen resistance.

Key words: fungicide resistance, plant pathogenic fungi, biocontrol

FLUDIOXONIL RESISTANCE PROFILING OF *Penicillium expansum* FROM STORED APPLE FRUITS IN SERBIA

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Penicillium expansum Link (1809) is the main causal agent of apple blue mold, leading to significant postharvest losses worldwide and impacting food safety due to mycotoxin production. Traditional management of blue mold relies on fungicide application. However, decreasing the number of approved active substances has narrowed the range of available fungicides with diverse modes of action, increasing the risk of resistance development in pathogen populations. Since fungicides based on the active ingredient fludioxonil are among the most used for apple blue mold control in Serbia, this study assessed the sensitivity of 65 *P. expansum* isolates originating from 26 apple storage facilities across the country. Isolates were characterized as *P. expansum* based on morphological characteristics and molecular analysis of two genes (*beta tubulin* and *calmodulin*). Growth rates were compared on four culture media to evaluate phenotypic variability. Resistance to fludioxonil was assessed *in vitro* at concentrations of 0.5 and 1 µg/mL incorporated into the growth medium, using colony diameter as an indicator of growth inhibition. Colony growth depended on strain identity and fludioxonil concentration with colony diameters ranging from 26–49 mm in the untreated control, 4–19 mm at 0.5 µg/mL fludioxonil treatment, and 0–16 mm at 1 µg/mL fludioxonil treatment. At 0.5 µg/mL fludioxonil, none of the 65 isolates were fully inhibited and 42 exhibited < 80% inhibition rates (lowest 49.78% for isolate P13), whereas at 1 µg/mL, 15 isolates were completely inhibited and only isolate P21 showed < 60% inhibition (59.66%). The results from this study emphasize the need for regular monitoring of fungicide efficacy and the development of integrated postharvest disease management strategies to minimize the chemical resistance and maintain fruit quality and safety.

Key words: Antifungal resistance, *Penicillium expansum*, Serbia

CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACHES TO MITIGATING ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE IN AGRICULTURE

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) poses a growing threat to global public health, with agricultural practices—particularly in the veterinary sector—recognized as significant contributors to the emergence and spread of resistant pathogens. This paper explores how circular economy (CE) principles can be strategically applied within the veterinary and agri-food systems to reduce reliance on antimicrobials and curb the development of resistance. Through a systematic review of recent literature, we analyze CE-based interventions such as nutrient recycling, improved manure management, wastewater treatment, bioconversion of organic waste, and the integration of alternative therapies (e.g., probiotics, phytogenics) into livestock production systems. Emphasis is placed on preventive health strategies, resource optimization, and system redesign as core circular principles relevant to AMR mitigation. The findings suggest that CE offers a promising interdisciplinary framework that not only aligns with One Health objectives but also enhances biosecurity, animal welfare, and long-term agricultural sustainability. However, effective implementation requires coordinated policy support, investment in innovation, and cross-sectoral collaboration. This review highlights the need for veterinary professionals to actively participate in the design and promotion of circular solutions that reduce antimicrobial dependence while preserving productivity and animal health.

Keywords: antimicrobial resistance, circular economy, veterinary medicine, sustainable agriculture

THE IMPORTANCE OF PROPER INTERPRETATION OF ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY TESTING IN SMALL ANIMAL PRACTICE

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Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) is essential for guiding effective antimicrobial therapy and monitoring the resistance trends. Among the widely used phenotypic methods, the *disc diffusion method* (Kirby-Bauer) remains a cost-effective and standardised method that evaluates the zones of inhibition around antibiotic-impregnated discs. For quantitative determination, the *broth and agar dilution methods* provide minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values by exposing microorganisms to serial antibiotic dilutions in liquid or solid media, respectively. The *E-test*, a gradient diffusion method, combines the antibiotics diffusion with MIC quantification, and offers high precision for a wide range of microorganisms and antibiotics. In clinical settings that require high throughput and automation, systems such as *VITEK 2* are increasingly employed. These automated platforms utilise proprietary cards and advanced algorithms to rapidly identify pathogens and determine antimicrobial susceptibility using optical or fluorescence-based sensors. In addition to general susceptibility profiling, these methods are also critical for the detection of specific resistance mechanisms in clinically important pathogens. Laboratory identification of bacterial resistance mechanisms in clinical isolates is essential not only for appropriate antibiotic therapy but also for controlling the spread of multidrug-resistant bacteria. The tests are performed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) and the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). The production of extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL) in bacteria of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family is assessed using the disc diffusion method with cefotaxime and ceftazidime, both with and without clavulanic acid as a beta-lactamase inhibitor. The detection of AmpC beta-lactamases that are not inhibited by clavulanic acid, is carried out using ceftiofuran discs as a screening method. Ceftiofuran discs are also used to detect methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), while methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* (MRSP) is detected using an oxacillin disc. The presence of carbapenemase enzymes is evaluated using the meropenem disc, but confirmation by a phenotypic Carba NP test is mandatory. Due to the unreliability of the disc diffusion method and the E-test for colistin resistance, the broth microdilution method is recommended, which determines the MIC that prevents bacterial growth, in accordance with ISO 20776-1:2020. The final confirmation of the listed phenotypic tests is performed using molecular methods, primarily the polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which enables the detection of antibiotic resistance genes.

Key words: resistance, antibiogram, MIC, E-test, phenotypic tests, molecular methods

Acknowledgement: This work was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

EVALUATION OF THE DIETARY EFFECT OF OLIVE PULP ON THE GUT MICROBIOTA OF LAYING HENS HOUSED IN AN ALTERNATIVE PRODUCTION SYSTEM

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The widespread use of antibiotics in farm animals, including poultry, for growth promotion and disease prevention has raised concerns about antimicrobial resistance (AMR), which could cause up to 10 million deaths annually by 2050. Recognizing this threat, the World Health Organization (WHO) has classified AMR as one of the top ten global public health threats, prompting international efforts to reduce antibiotic use. The EU has banned antibiotics as growth promoters and further restricted their prophylactic use in livestock under the 2023 Veterinary Medicines Regulation. Consequently, there is a growing need for alternative feed additives that support intestinal health and immune protection in animals without relying on antibiotics. In this concept, the incorporation of phytogetic feed additives such as olive pulp (OP), rich in bioactive compounds like polyphenols, dietary fiber, and unsaturated fatty acids, with antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, into laying hens' diets appears to be a promising alternative to antibiotics. The use of agro-industrial by-products like OP, as natural antimicrobials also aligns with consumer preferences for more sustainable animal production practices. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the dietary effect of OP on the gut microbiota of laying hens housed in an alternative production system. This study was conducted on a commercial poultry farm in Greece. A total of 180 Isa Brown layers, aged 23 weeks, were assigned to 15-floor littered pens with wood shavings (12 hens per pen) in compliance with EU Directive 1999/74/EC, and divided into three feeding groups (CON, OP4, and OP6) based on the dietary level of OP. The CON group, which served as a control, was fed a basal layer diet. The OP groups were fed with the CON diet supplemented with 4% and 6% olive pulp (OP4 and OP6, respectively). The dried OP used in this study was a commercial product in flour form, which replaced a quantity of soymeal and of soya oil in the CON diet. Finally, three isonitrogenous and isocaloric rations were formulated. Fecal samples were collected at three time points for microbiota analysis: 22 weeks of age (before adding OP to the hens' diet), 39 and 59 weeks of age. Metagenomic analysis revealed that fecal microbial diversity was affected only by hens' age ($p < 0.05$) and not by OP treatment ($p > 0.05$). At the phylum level, *Actinomycetota* was most abundant (14.7 to 62.5%), followed by *Bacillota* (25.0 to 54.3%) and *Pseudomonadota* (4.6 to 22.3%). However, pairwise comparisons between treatment groups at 59 weeks of age clearly showed that the relative abundance of *Megasphaera stantonii* and *Megamonas hypermegale* increased with the increase in OP dose ($p < 0.05$). Significant differences were observed between CON and OP groups ($p < 0.05$) as well as between OP4 and OP6 groups ($p < 0.05$). These bacteria species belong to the core microbiota in both broilers and layers. They are involved in the fermentation of dietary fiber and carbohydrates and produce Short Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs) such as propionate and butyrate. These SCFAs serve as important energy sources for the host and play a crucial role in maintaining gut health by lowering the pH and inhibiting the growth and colonization of several pathogens like *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, and *Shigella* spp., to maintain a stable microbial environment. Overall, our study suggests that the addition of OP to the diet of laying hens promotes the proliferation of *Megasphaera stantonii* and *Megamonas hypermegale* SCFA-producing bacteria involved in the degradation of

complex plant compounds, potentially contributing to the overall health of the gut microbiota of laying hens.

Key words: olive pulp; laying hens; phytogetic feed additives; alternatives to antibiotics; gut health; sustainability

Acknowledgements: This research was carried out as part of the project entitled “Production of an egg with a high content of fatty acids beneficial to the consumer, by adding olive pulp to laying hens’ diet” (Project code: KMP6-0084177) under the framework of the Action “Investment Plans of Innovation” of the Program “Central Macedonia 2021–2027”, which is co-funded by the European Union and Greece.

PRECISION MEDICINE GUIDELINE FOR TARGETED ANTIBACTERIAL ADMINISTRATION IN NEONATAL LAMBS WITH DIARRHEA SYNDROME

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Neonatal Diarrhea Syndrome (NDS) is considered as the leading cause of mortality in lambs less than 20 days of age. Most outbreaks have a multifactorial etiology and usually involve *Cryptosporidium* spp., rotavirus, and *E. coli* strains. Treatment is usually based on antimicrobial agents, but such treatment should be justified and considered mainly in systemically ill animals. Therefore, there is a need to establish specific clinical guidelines for using antimicrobials in cases of NDS in lambs. This study aimed to propose an evidence-based clinical guideline for selective administration of antimicrobials to lambs with NDS and to evaluate its efficacy under field conditions. According to the proposed treatment protocol, all lambs with diarrhea were to be allowed to suckle voluntarily and given an electrolyte mixture by oral drenching once daily until recovery; antimicrobials and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) were to be administered only in cases with a combination of at least two of the following clinical signs: fever/hypothermia, anorexia, depression and scleral congestion. In cases with pyrexia alone, only NSAIDs were to be administered. Antimicrobials without NSAIDs should be given to lambs with prolonged diarrhea, lasting more than 5 days, and none of the aforementioned clinical signs. Selection of the appropriate compound was to be based on antimicrobial susceptibility testing. The above protocol was evaluated on a dairy sheep farm where 66 lambs out of 73 that were born within one month, developed NDS. All lambs were clinically examined daily since birth and were evaluated for diarrhea; a three-point scale was employed for fecal scoring with 0 = normal, 1 = intermediate and 2 = watery feces, and the score was recorded. Lambs exhibiting a fecal score of 1 or higher were classified as having diarrhea. The diarrheic state was considered to have ceased when the fecal score returned to 0 for 24 hours. Lambs with diarrhea underwent a thorough clinical examination daily until recovery. The antimicrobial agents used, when needed, were a combination of ampicillin and dicloxacillin based on the results of the antimicrobial susceptibility testing using Vitek 2 and following the interpretative criteria of CLSI. The NSAID used was meloxicam. The average duration of diarrhea was 3.9 days. Pyrexia alone was detected in approximately 26% of the animals. In 15% of the diarrheic lambs, pyrexia was initially detected, and further symptoms developed over the following days. Antibacterials alone or in combination with NSAIDs were administered in about 33% of the lambs. From the lambs of the last category, 18% received only antibacterials due to prolonged diarrhea, 36% had scleral congestion and pyrexia, approximately 14% had scleral congestion, pyrexia and depression, 9% had scleral congestion and depression and 4.5% for each one of the following combinations pyrexia - depression, hypothermia - depression, scleral congestion - hypothermia - depression, hypothermia - scleral congestion and depression - anorexia. The mortality rate was 1.5%. The suggested protocol, based only on clinical signs, was proven effective in treating lambs with NDS. Pyrexia alone is not a strong indication for antibacterial administration. Therefore, the decision to use antibacterials should not be based on the presence of pyrexia alone, but on the combination of at least two clinical signs suggestive of bacteremia.

Keywords: diarrhea syndrome, neonatal lambs, treatment, antimicrobials, guideline

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PROFILES OF BACTERIAL ISOLATES FROM PET RABBITS IN SPAIN

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is an increasingly concerning global health issue. The close contact between pets and their owners can facilitate the transmission of resistant bacteria. Up to now, research on AMR in pet rabbits remains very limited. Our study analyzed 3,596 clinical samples, submitted to a Spanish veterinary diagnostic laboratory between 2010 and 2021. Microbiological identification was achieved in 2,998 cases (83.4%), while 598 samples were negative (no bacterial growth). Most of the samples submitted were associated with respiratory problems (53%), otitis (18%), or cutaneous abscesses around the head (16%). The most frequently identified bacterial agents were *Staphylococcus* spp. (15.8%), *Pseudomonas* spp. (12.7%), *Pasteurella* spp. (10.0%), *Bordetella* spp. (9.6%), and *Streptococcus* spp. (6.8%). Enterobacteriaceae, mainly *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Enterobacter cloacae*, accounted for approximately 18% of the isolates and were associated with a wide range of pathological conditions. Less frequently identified microorganisms included *Acinetobacter* spp. (3.8%), *Pantoea* spp. (3.0%), *Enterococcus* spp. (2.6%), *Moraxella* spp. (2.6%), *Serratia* spp. (1.8%), *Neisseria* spp. (1.6%), *Proteus* spp. (1.1%), *Trueperella* spp. (1.1%), *Stenotrophomonas* spp. (0.9%), and *Burkholderia* spp. (0.8%). Regarding antimicrobial susceptibility testing, multidrug resistance (MDR) was defined as resistance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial classes, excluding intrinsic resistance from the analysis. The species showing the highest levels of resistance—on average to five antimicrobial classes—were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Burkholderia* spp. Within Enterobacteriaceae, high MDR rates were observed in *K. pneumoniae* (58%), *E. coli* (48%), and *E. cloacae* (36%). In contrast, infections caused by *Staphylococcus* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., and *Pasteurella multocida* were highly sensitive to conventional veterinary antimicrobials (EMA categories D and C). In conclusion, pet rabbits in Spain show an emerging presence of nosocomial MDR pathogens such as *P. aeruginosa*, *S. maltophilia*, and *K. pneumoniae*, which may underline a significant public health concern. Considering that many of the predominant bacteria identified in this study are among the main pathogens involved in human hospital-associated infections due to AMR, it is essential for both medical and veterinary professionals to work together to optimize and rationalize the prudent use of antibiotics in pets and humans, under the One Health approach.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Multidrug resistance, Spain

IMPORTANCE OF SELECTIVE DRY COW TREATMENT IN REDUCE OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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Mastitis is one of the most important diseases in dairy cows. It is defined as an inflammation of the mammary gland caused by various factors. The most common cause of mastitis is bacteria, which is why antibiotics are widely used in the treatment of mastitis. The dry period refers to the stage of lactation when the cow is not milked, and during this time, the mammary gland is prepared for the next lactation. In dairy farming, a large quantity of antibiotics is used to prevent mastitis during the dry period. At the same time, antibiotics are used unnecessarily even in uninfected animals. This irrational use of antibiotics has led to the increasing development of antimicrobial resistance. For this reason, more countries are transitioning to a selective dry cow treatment, which involves using antibiotics only for cows with infected mammary gland. This approach includes examining the mammary gland, detecting infections, and measuring the somatic cell count in the milk before drying. The treatment of cows with infected mammary gland includes the use of antibiotics based on bacteriological culture of the milk, while cows with uninfected udder are treated with internal teat sealants only, without antibiotics. This approach reduces the uncontrolled and irrational use of antibiotics in dairy farming, leading to a significant reduce in the spread of antimicrobial resistance.

Key words: cows, mastitis, dry period, antimicrobial resistance

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Contract no. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117].

METAGENOMIC SEQUENCING IN CLINICAL ASSESSMENT OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE POTENTIAL IN COMPLEX MICROBIOLOGICAL SAMPLES

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the most pressing public health challenges. Targeted antibiotic (AB) use can help reduce the emergence and spread of AMR while improving treatment efficacy. Achieving this requires an understanding of the antibiotic susceptibility of the pathogens involved in the disease. However, traditional antibiotic susceptibility testing (AST) analyzes the easily culturable subset of bacteria present in the disease process, limiting its scope. Next- and third-generation sequencing technologies enable the identification of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) within a bacterial community. This metagenomic approach allows us to map the complete set of ARGs and define the concept of the so-called antimicrobial resistance potential (AMRP) of complex, multi-bacterial microbiological samples. To evaluate the interpretability of AMRP, we assessed the concordance between phenotypic AMR characteristics and ARGs using data from 574 *Escherichia coli* strains across five studies. The findings indicate that for 44% of the studied antibiotics, phenotypically resistant strains exhibit a 90% probability of resistance based on genotype. Meanwhile, for 92% of antibiotics, phenotypically susceptible strains are genotypically susceptible with a 90% probability. Overall, ARG detection predicted phenotypic resistance with at least 90% confidence for 67% of antibiotics. The likelihood of incorrectly identifying a phenotypically susceptible strain as resistant based on genotype is below 5% for 92% of antibiotics. Similarly, the probability of misclassifying a phenotypically resistant strain as susceptible is below 5% for 44% of antibiotics. Given these strain-level concordance results, we can reasonably infer that similar patterns hold true for bacteria in complex microbial samples. This suggests that AMRP derived from metagenomic ARG analysis can guide the selection of effective antibiotics. This concept is illustrated through AMRP analysis of a canine external otitis sample.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Genomics, Complex microbial sample, Clinical metagenomics

Acknowledgements: The study was supported by the strategic research fund of the University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest (Grant No. SRF-001), and the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program supports the project under Grant Agreement No. 874735 (VEO). Further funding source, Project no. 2024-2.1.2-EKÖP-2024-00018 has been implemented with the support provided by the Ministry of Culture and Innovation of Hungary from the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund, financed under the 2024-2.1.2-EKÖP funding scheme.

POULTRY LITTER IN ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE CHAIN: RISKS AND BIOSECURITY MEASURES

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Driven by rising global demand for poultry meat and eggs, the poultry sector has grown significantly in recent decades. Notably, poultry production ranks as one of the highest consumers of veterinary antibiotics, and research suggests that 30–90% of these compounds are excreted in feces or urine, either in their unchanged form or as bioactive metabolites. Consequently, poultry litter, which is used as a significant organic fertilizer in agriculture, can serve as a reservoir of antimicrobial residues, resistant bacteria, and antimicrobial resistance genes, thus potentially posing a threat to the surrounding ecosystem. Penicillins, tetracyclines and quinolones represent the primary antibiotic classes linked to resistance spread through poultry litter. After being used in agricultural fields, these pollutants can end up on crops and thus enter the human or animal food chain. Antimicrobial residues from the litter can lead to the selection of resistant bacteria in the soil. Also, as a result of contact between resistant bacteria and soil bacteria, resistance genes can be exchanged through horizontal gene exchange. Furthermore, soil leaching and surface runoff can contribute to these pollutants reaching surface and groundwater. The use of such water for irrigation leads to a feedback loop that sustains the presence and mobility of resistance determinants in agricultural systems. Considering these risks, within the framework of a comprehensive fight against antimicrobial resistance, it is necessary to develop effective strategies for processing poultry litter as organic fertilizer, which will eliminate, or at least reduce, the risk of spreading antibiotic residues and resistant bacteria into the environment. Composting is one of the most common and practical methods of litter processing, which leads to a reduction in microbial load and the inactivation of various compounds, including antimicrobial drugs. The application of poultry litter on agricultural fields should be properly timed to optimize its fertilizing effect and to reduce the risk of crop contamination. Rainy periods should be avoided for litter application to prevent the leaching and runoff of potential contaminants into surface and groundwater. Despite all preventive measures aimed at limiting the environmental spread of antimicrobial resistance, the most critical interventions must still occur during poultry production, primarily through reducing antibiotic use or replacing them with alternative strategies. Only through continuous monitoring, adherence to biosecurity procedures, and commitment to the One Health concept across all levels of production can the spread of antimicrobial resistance be effectively controlled and public health protected.

Key words: poultry litter, antimicrobial resistance, biosecurity

PHENOTYPIC COMPARISON OF BETA-LACTAMASE AND EXTENDED SPECTRUM BETA-LACTAMASE (ESBL) PRODUCTION IN *ESCHERICHIA COLI* ISOLATES FROM POULTRY AND SWINE SAMPLES IN HUNGARY

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The presence and spread of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* strains in livestock production is an increasing global concern, particularly considering the One Health concept and its implications for antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Continuous monitoring of beta-lactamase and extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) producing strains is of particular importance, as the production of these enzymes poses significant therapeutic challenges in both human and veterinary medicine. Our study aimed to compare the phenotypic frequency of beta-lactamase and ESBL production in *E. coli* isolates from large-scale poultry and swine farms in Hungary. A total of 881 poultry-derived and 203 swine-derived *E. coli* strains were isolated and analysed. Phenotypic determination of beta-lactamase and ESBL production was carried out using minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) testing. Following the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) protocol, beta-lactamase production was evaluated based on the MIC values of amoxicillin and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, while ESBL production was assessed using the MIC values of cefotaxime and cefotaxime-clavulanic acid. A reduction of at least threefold in MIC in the presence of clavulanic acid was interpreted as indicative of enzyme production. Among the poultry isolates, 34% were identified as beta-lactamase producers, while ESBL production was detected in 6% of the strains. In contrast, among the swine-derived isolates, the proportion of beta-lactamase producers was considerably higher (54%), and the prevalence of ESBL-producing strains reached 63%. This marked difference between the two animal species raises questions about the impact of antimicrobial use practices in swine production. Based on our findings, we conclude that *E. coli* strains from swine harbour beta-lactamase and ESBL-producing phenotypes at a significantly higher rate than those isolated from poultry. This difference is likely associated with varying antibiotic usage patterns and differences in microbiological environments across husbandry systems. The results highlight the importance of targeted AMR surveillance programs in livestock and may support the optimisation of antimicrobial use. Further studies are needed to explore the genetic background and horizontal transfer potential of resistance genes in greater detail.

Keywords: AMR, beta-lactamase, ESBL, MDR, Hungary, poultry, swine

Acknowledgements: Supported by the Normative Research Funding Committee (NRC), University of Veterinary Medicine, Budapest. Project no. RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00001 has been implemented with the support provided by the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), financed under the National Recovery Fund budget estimate, RRF-2.3.1-21 funding scheme.

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT INFECTIONS IN PEDIATRIC SURGERY: TREATMENT OF MDR INFECTIONS IN A PATIENT AFTER CORRECTIVE SCOLIOSIS SURGERY

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Antibiotic resistance represents a major challenge in modern medicine, especially in hospital settings, where infections caused by multidrug-resistant microorganisms are increasingly common. The treatment of these infections is often complex, with a limited number of effective antibiotics, prolonged hospitalizations, and high clinical risks, particularly in pediatric patients with comorbidities. A 10-year-old girl with spinal muscular atrophy and neuromuscular scoliosis was hospitalized for corrective scoliosis surgery. The intervention was uneventful; however, on the tenth postoperative day, she developed fever, wound dehiscence, and purulent discharge from the surgical wound. Empirical antibiotic therapy (cefazolin, amikacin) and fluconazole were initiated. During the postoperative course, *Enterococcus faecium*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida* spp. were isolated, and the therapy was changed (tigecycline, clindamycin). After two weeks, her condition worsened, with the development of pneumonia, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterobacter hormaechei*, and *Enterococcus faecalis* were isolated from the wound. Therapy was adjusted accordingly. During her further hospitalization, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, resistant to most antibiotics but sensitive to colistin and intermediately resistant to imipenem-cilastatin, was isolated from the wound. Anaerobic bacteria (*Bacteroides fragilis*, *Streptococcus parasanguinis*) sensitive to clindamycin were also detected. During the hospitalization, the girl experienced two urinary tract infections, the first caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, treated with imipenem-cilastatin, and the second caused by *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Citrobacter koseri*, which showed sensitivity to ciprofloxacin. The wound was regularly dressed under general anesthesia with the application of a VAC system. After four months, the patient was discharged in stable condition. This case highlights the challenges in treating MDR infections in pediatric patients with comorbidities. Microbiological diagnostics and personalized therapy are crucial for effective management. The rise of resistant microorganisms, particularly in pediatric surgery, emphasizes the need for early identification and targeted therapy. Prolonged hospital stays increase the risk of such infections, making a tailored, multidimensional approach essential. The treatment of MDR infections requires timely diagnostics, a multidisciplinary approach, and rational use of antibiotics. This case highlights the importance of an individualized treatment approach in pediatric surgery.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance, MDR, pediatric surgery, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, microbiological diagnostic

INVESTIGATION OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE IN BIOCONTROL-INTENDED *Bacillus* ISOLATES FROM VINEYARD

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The discovery of antibiotics marked a revolutionary breakthrough in medicine, enabling the effective treatment of previously fatal bacterial infections, enhancing livestock production, and contributing significantly to socio-economic development. However, the irresponsible and excessive use of antibiotics has led to the emergence of antibiotic resistance, which is now recognized as one of the most pressing global threats to public health. In this context, careful consideration must be given to the selection and application of microorganisms across various sectors, including medicine, agriculture, and industrial biotechnology, to ensure they neither harbour nor disseminate antibiotic resistance genes. The use of resistant strains or those capable of horizontal gene transfer can facilitate the spread of resistance within microbial communities in different ecological niches, including pathogenic species, thereby compromising the efficacy of antimicrobial therapies and posing serious risks to public health. In this study, several *Bacillus* strains were isolated from vineyard soil and grape berries with the aim of evaluating their potential as biocontrol agents in agricultural systems. As one of the initial steps in evaluating their suitability for such applications, a comprehensive assessment of their antibiotic resistance profiles was performed. In vitro susceptibility testing was conducted using the disc-diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar. The results were interpreted based on inhibition zone diameters: isolates were considered susceptible (≥ 21 mm), moderately susceptible (16-20 mm), or resistant (≤ 15 mm). The presence of resistance genes was assessed using the PCR (polymerase chain reaction) method based on utilization of the specific primer pairs. Several antimicrobial resistance genes associated with different resistance mechanisms, namely *penp*, *bla* OXA, *VmiR*, *lmrB*, *ant-6*, *aac-3*, *tetL*, and *mphK*, were selected as PCR targets. *Bacillus* sp. 12R, isolated from vineyard soil, exhibited resistance to β -lactam antibiotics, specifically penicillin, oxacillin, piperacillin, and ampicillin, as well as to lincosamides, including lincomycin and clindamycin. The resistance genes *ant-6* and *mphK*, encoding resistance to aminoglycosides and macrolides respectively, were detected in this isolate. Despite the presence of the *mphK* gene, *Bacillus* sp. 12R demonstrated high susceptibility to macrolide antibiotics, with mean inhibition zone diameters of 40.33 ± 0.29 mm for erythromycin, 41.00 ± 0.50 mm for azithromycin, and 28.67 ± 0.58 mm for clarithromycin. Among aminoglycosides, moderate susceptibility was observed for tobramycin (18.33 ± 0.58 mm) and neomycin (19.33 ± 0.29 mm), while high susceptibility was detected for kanamycin (28.67 ± 0.29 mm), amikacin (28.67 ± 0.58 mm), and streptomycin (40.00 ± 0.00 mm). In contrast, *Bacillus* sp. 18B showed *in vitro* resistance only to oxacillin, aztreonam, and methicillin from the β -lactam group of antibiotics. Moderate susceptibility was observed to aminoglycoside antibiotics, including tobramycin, amikacin and kanamycin, with inhibition zones ranging from 16.00 ± 0.00 to 18.33 ± 0.58 mm, while the remaining tested antibiotics showed inhibition zones greater than 21 mm, indicating susceptibility. Notably, no antimicrobial resistance genes were detected in this isolate. These results underscore the concerning trend of antibiotic resistance in bacteria originating from natural environments and highlight the urgent need for further research and the development of strategies to mitigate this issue. In the context of biocontrol agricultural applications, a careful screening of candidate strains for resistance traits is essential to ensure their safe application to prevent the unintentional spread of antimicrobial resistance within agroecosystems.

Keywords: antibiotic resistance, *Bacillus* spp., disc-diffusion method, resistance genes, PCR, agriculture

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #14906, Eco-innovative circular bioprocess design for grey mold management in wine production – EcoInvent.

PROBIOTIC CELL-FREE SUPERNATANTS VS. VIABLE CELLS: ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY AGAINST *KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE* IN WOUND CARE

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The rise of Gram-negative pathogens poses a serious threat to public health due to their high resistance to existing antibiotics and lack of novel therapeutic options. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is one of the pathogens frequently isolated from chronic wounds, where it contributes to delayed healing, increased inflammation, and consequently, enhanced risk of complications. Its ability to withstand conventional treatments highlights the urgent need for alternative antimicrobial strategies, especially as multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains become increasingly prevalent. This challenge is further amplified in the context of diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs), a serious complication of the metabolic disease diabetes mellitus. In these wounds, sustained hyperglycemia creates an ideal environment for bacterial colonization and immune dysfunction, making infection control particularly difficult. The dual burden of impaired healing and MDR infections calls for innovative approaches that target both microbial and metabolic dysregulation. Probiotics are emerging as promising candidates due to their antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties. In this study, four probiotic strains, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, and *Lactobacillus gasseri*, were evaluated for their ability to inhibit a resistant strain of *K. pneumoniae*. Cultures were grown under anaerobic conditions, and both cell-free supernatants and viable cells were prepared and tested in simulated wound fluid under microaerophilic conditions. To replicate diabetic wound environments, experiments were conducted under both hyperglycemic and normoglycemic conditions (20 mM and 5 mM, respectively) over 24 hours. Among the supernatants, *L. plantarum* demonstrated the most potent antimicrobial effect in both environments while *L. gasseri* was the least effective showing that glucose levels had little impact on the efficacy of cell-free supernatants. On the other hand, the antimicrobial activity of live probiotic cells was clearly influenced by glucose concentration. Under hyperglycemic conditions, *L. rhamnosus* and *L. plantarum* reduced *K. pneumoniae* growth by approximately fourfold and fivefold, respectively, whereas their efficacy was diminished under normoglycemic conditions. These findings suggest that select probiotic strains, particularly *L. rhamnosus* and *L. plantarum*, may serve as effective antimicrobial agents against *K. pneumoniae*, especially in the hyperglycemic environment characteristic of diabetic wounds. This highlights their potential role in the development of targeted, adjunctive therapies for managing DFUs complicated by resistant Gram-negative infections.

Key words: *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus gasseri*, normoglycemic, hyperglycemic

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, Grant No 9802, Activated Charcoal as a Carrier of Probiotics: A New Approach for Pathogen Elimination in Wounds-ProHealingAC

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE PROFILES OF BACTERIAL PATHOGENS ISOLATED FROM CANINE KERATITIS

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Bacterial keratitis is a common ophthalmological condition with complications that can lead to impaired vision and possibly eye loss. Corneal damage, often resulting from eye injuries, tends to develop infections due to the presence of conjunctival microflora. Although initial empirical treatment of both conditions should target the most common bacterial pathogens using broad-spectrum antibiotics, prolonged inappropriate therapy with inadequate drug selection or frequency of use can lead to serious consequences such as keratomalacia, scarring, perforation, vision loss, or loss of the eye. The aim of this study was to analyze the most commonly isolated bacteria from microbiological corneal swabs and compare the results of antimicrobial susceptibility testing with commercially available topical antimicrobial agents for empirical therapy. For this research, archived data were collected from all dogs that underwent special ophthalmologic examinations from January 2024 to March 2025, in which a microbiological corneal swab was taken. Clinical specimens were cultured using standard microbiological techniques. Identification of bacterial isolates was performed using Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS). Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) was conducted using the broth microdilution method, and results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. Of the seven microbiological corneal swabs, bacteria were isolated in 57.14% of the samples, while the remaining 42.86% showed a negative result. All dogs had previously undergone topical antimicrobial therapy, and in two cases, they had also received systemic antibiotic therapy. Despite the obvious clinical signs of keratitis, the negative bacteriological result may be related to the previous systemic use of antibiotics, which reduced the number of bacteria on the corneal surface and made their isolation impossible. Among the positive bacteriologic corneal swabs, *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius* was isolated in 50% of cases, while individual samples contained *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus salivarius*. The most frequently used antimicrobial preparations in empirical treatment were neomycin (42.86%), tobramycin (28.57%), and chloramphenicol (28.57%). The isolated bacteria were resistant to penicillins in 50% of cases, which can be related to the use of penicillins as a first-line systemic antibiotic. Resistance to aminoglycosides and phenicols developed in 25% of cases. In 50% of cases, antimicrobial resistance was present to the same group of antibiotics used as topical antimicrobial therapy before the swab was taken. Although bacteria were isolated in more than half of the samples, there is also a significant prevalence of antimicrobial resistance, particularly to penicillins and other antibiotics previously used in therapy. This preliminary study provides valuable information for future research on the occurrence and monitoring of antimicrobial resistance associated with the overuse of topical antimicrobial therapy or inadequate selection of antimicrobial agents in the treatment of bacterial keratitis.

Keywords: corneal infection, antimicrobial susceptibility testing, antimicrobial therapy

RESIDUES OF VETERINARY MEDICINAL PRODUCTS ON THE PLATE: INSIGHTS FROM RASFF NOTIFICATIONS

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Veterinary medicinal products are used to prevent or treat animal diseases, or even to promote animal growth, which can result in residues in food. Among numerous associated harmful effects, antimicrobial resistance stands out as particularly concerning. This overview of food contamination with residues of veterinary medicinal products is based on the Rapid Alert System of Food and Feed (RASFF) data over 2020–2024. During these five years, 181 notifications reported the presence of at least one veterinary drug residue. In the majority of cases, the food originated from Vietnam (50; most commonly fish/fish products and crustaceans/crustacean products), followed by India (19; mostly crustaceans), Poland (18; meat/poultry and products), the Netherlands (14; meat/meat products), Belgium (10; meat/poultry and products), and others. Food categories and the most frequently reported residue classes were meat/meat products (54) – nitrofurans derivatives (9; 6 furazolidone, 3 nitrofurazone), tetracyclines (7; 3 doxycycline, 3 oxytetracycline, 1 tetracycline), crustaceans/crustacean products (41) – nitrofurans derivatives (18; 17 furazolidone; 1 nitrofurazone), triphenylmethane dye (11; leucomalachite/malachite green), fish/fish products (37) – triphenyl/triaryl methane dye (23 leucomalachite/malachite green, 8 leucocrystal/crystal violet), and poultry/poultry products (26) - tetracyclines (14; 12 doxycycline, 1 chlortetracycline, 1 oxytetracycline), while significantly fewer notifications were related to honey (9) - amphenicols (2 chloramphenicol), fluoroquinolones (2; 1 ciprofloxacin, 1 enrofloxacin), eggs/egg products (9) – tetracyclines (3 doxycycline), fluoroquinolones (3 enrofloxacin), milk/dairy products (2) – beta-lactams, amphenicols, other food product/mixed (2) – amphenicols, and cephalopods/cephalopod products (1) – tetracyclines. Co-occurrence of residues is recorded in 17 cases, among which stand out one with 4 and four with 3 residues each. The contaminated foods were mostly considered to pose a serious human health risk (47.5%). Veterinary medicinal products must be strictly controlled and monitored to protect consumers of animal-origin foods. In this context, the RASFF system is a key factor in safeguarding public health in the EU and beyond.

Keywords: food of animal origin, food safety, public health, risk assessment

OPTIMAL PREPARATION OF PIGLETS AS A TOOL FOR REDUCING THE USE OF ANTIBIOTICS

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Diarrhea is a key issue affecting piglet performance during the initial two weeks post-weaning, leading to economic losses, increased antibiotic use, rising antimicrobial resistance and compromised animal welfare (Witjes et al., 2024; Pons et al., 2025). The goal of the research was to explore the possibility of raising piglets without relying on antibiotics. The observation involved 34 piglets (genotype TN70 x DP), which were divided into two equal groups post-weaning. At birth, all piglets received oral treatment with IgY, *Enterococcus faecium* (500 x 10⁹ CFU/kg), vitamins A (670,000 IU/kg), D3 (67,000 IU/kg), and E (67 mg/kg), dextroglucose and soybean oil (“Piglobin®”, 4 ml per pig) as an energy and immunity booster. During the suckling phase, they were supplemented with a milk replacer containing probiotics *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus subtilis* 1.3 x 10⁹ CFU/kg in a 1:1 ratio (“SanAmmat Puddino®”, 19% CP), with each pig consuming about 0.4 kg from days 2 to 26. The mortality rate in the farrowing pens was 10.53%, which is considered acceptable. After weaning, the piglets were grouped by sex and body weight (5.99 vs 5.98 kg/head; p > 0.05). Both groups were fed a dry prestarter feed (“Bonni-M Forte®”, 85%) with 18% CP and 16.50 MJ ME, supplemented with a booster (“SUSan MultiVital®”, 15%) containing 20% CP and 17.00 MJ ME. Feed intake was around 2 kg per piglet (p > 0.05). Post-weaning, all piglets were administered “Antilaxan®” (2.5% CP) via water for three days. This product contained a blend of IgY, MOS, FOS, apple pectin, lignocellulose, carob, banana, carrot, blueberry, chamomile powder, and probiotics including *E. faecium* (1.0 x 10¹¹ CFU/kg), *B. subtilis*, and *B. licheniformis* (3.2 x 10¹⁰ CFU/kg in a 1:1 ratio). Average consumption was 28.5 g per piglet (p > 0.05). Additionally, the piglets received organic acids (“Acidosan®”, 0.2%) via water at 5 ml per pig for five days (p > 0.05) after weaning. Starting at 33 days of age, group A received starter feed with 12.72 MJ ME, 16.81% CP (supplementary feed mix “Protamino Pigg Start®”) while group B received starter feed with 13.70 MJ ME, 16.64% CP (supplementary feed mix “PreKern Forte 3®”). Both starters were fortified with formic acid, calcium citrate, and butyric acid (“Sanocid®”, 0.5%; “ButySan®”, 0.2%). Piglets were fed until day 51, after which they were weighed. Modified fecal scoring method (Peltoniemi and Oliviero, 2015), between days 33 and 40 showed differences between the groups. Group A had a mean fecal score of 3.00 and a color score of 2.47, while Group B scored 3.41 and 3.59 respectively, with significant differences (p = 0.004 and p = 0.000). The differences found were mainly due to the supplementary feed mix used to make the starter and the recipes used. No digestive disorders or antibiotic use were observed. Final weights differed significantly (p = 0.028), with group B averaging 13.36 kg and group A at 11.47 kg. No deaths were recorded between 26 and 51 days of age. The results of observation highlight that holistic approach with proper nutrition, probiotics, prebiotics, IgY, organic acids, phytobiotics, and strict farm hygiene, it is feasible to raise healthy piglets without antibiotics.

Key words: probiotics, prebiotics, phytobiotics, IgY, organic acids, fecal scoring, health status

ESSENTIAL OILS AS A SUPPLEMENTARY THERAPY WITH STANDARD ANTIBIOTIC TREATMENTS

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The global surge in antimicrobial resistance has intensified the search for effective, sustainable alternatives to conventional antibiotics. Essential oils have long been utilized as flavourings, fragrances, and natural preservatives in the food and feed industries. They have also been used in traditional medicine and more recently in modern approaches such as aromatherapy. With their emerging role as antimicrobial agents, essential oils show great potential in addressing the intricacies of drug-resistant infections in human, veterinary, and environmental health. Their multifaceted mechanisms of action, low toxicity, and natural origin position them as both effective standalone agents and potent adjuvants in combination therapies. Essential oils are composed of diverse bioactive molecules that target multiple sites within microbial cells, disrupting membranes, inhibiting enzymes, and interfering with quorum sensing. Unlike single-target synthetic drugs, this broad-spectrum, multi-pathway approach hinders the development of resistance, making essential oils especially suitable in the battle against multidrug-resistant pathogens. Numerous studies have demonstrated their synergistic potential when combined with traditional antibiotics, reducing the effective dosage of both agents while enhancing antimicrobial efficacy. For example, menthone and menthol are naturally occurring volatile organic compounds found in various essential oils with a minty flavor, such as peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) and other mint species like corn mint (*M. arvensis*) and pennyroyal (*M. pulegium*). These compounds exhibit antimicrobial activity against a broad spectrum of microorganisms, particularly gastrointestinal pathogens, and also promote wound healing. Additionally, thymol and carvacrol—structural isomers—possess significant antimicrobial properties. Thymol has a pleasant, herbal, aromatic odor, while carvacrol has a characteristic pungent, warm scent. These two compounds are characteristic of oregano (*Origanum* spp.), thyme (*Thymus* spp.), savory (*Satureja* spp.), ajwain (*Trachyspermum ammi*), and many other plants. Moreover, eugenol and isoeugenol are naturally occurring compounds known for their strong antibacterial properties, found in clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*), nutmeg (*Myristica* spp.), cinnamon (*Cinnamomum* spp.), basil (*Ocimum* spp.), bay leaf (*Laurus nobilis*), and others. Given the large number of volatile components isolated from essential oils, this list could continue indefinitely. Beyond their antimicrobial properties, essential oils play a vital role in holistic health practices, particularly in aromatherapy. Scientific exploration of aromatherapy has revealed its benefits not only for mental well-being but also for physical health. Essential oils are increasingly recognized as complementary therapies, often used in conjunction with pharmaceuticals to support immune function, reduce inflammation, and combat infections. In veterinary medicine, essential oils offer an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional antibiotics, especially in the treatment of infections in livestock. This is particularly important given the widespread overuse of antimicrobials in animal husbandry, a major contributor to global resistance trends. Despite their promising potential, further research is needed to standardize essential oil formulations, elucidate their mechanisms of action, and validate their efficacy across a range of pathogens and clinical settings. In conclusion, essential oils represent a dynamic and multifaceted approach to combating antimicrobial resistance. Their effectiveness against multidrug-resistant pathogens, biofilm-disrupting capabilities, synergy with conventional antibiotics, and wide applicability across human and veterinary medicine highlight their relevance in future antimicrobial strategies.

Key words: bioactive compounds, volatile compounds, antimicrobial resistance, multidrug-resistant pathogens, synergistic therapy, veterinary medicine

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, grant number: 451-03-136/2025-03/200032.

RESISTANCE ONSET DELAY: UV-C AS A NOVEL TOOL AGAINST GRAPEVINE POWDERY MILDEW

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Erysiphe necator, causal agent of grapevine powdery mildew is a major fungal pathogen that causes significant economic losses in grape production worldwide. Conventional disease management relies heavily on frequent applications of systemic fungicides, which raises concerns about pathogen resistance, environmental impact and potential risks to consumer health. As a result, there is increasing interest in developing alternative, more sustainable disease control strategies that minimize chemical input, while maintaining effective plant protection. Treatments with UV-C radiation have recently emerged as a potential solution for agricultural application and can be effective in controlling powdery mildew for a wide variety of crops. UV-C radiation causes direct damage to fungal DNA through the formation of cyclobutane pyrimidine dimers and 6–4 photoproducts, as well as inducing oxidative stress through reactive oxygen species, ultimately disrupting fungal cell function. Early attempts to use UV-C light in plant disease control were largely unsuccessful, as high doses applied during the daytime often resulted in plant tissue damage. Furthermore, studies have shown that grapevine powdery mildew has the ability to repair UV-C induced DNA damage through a photolyase mechanism driven by blue light and UV-A originating from the sun. Nighttime UV-C exposure solved these two main issues: it requires a lower non-phytotoxic dose of UV-C to achieve the same protective effect as daytime application, and it disrupts the DNA repair mechanism of the pathogens. In laboratory studies, UV-C light applied during darkness completely inhibited the germination of conidia of *E. necator*. Additionally, plants exposed to UV-C light days before inoculation with *E. necator* showed greater resistance. In field experiments, UV-C light in the form of 1-s flashes has been shown to stimulate plants' natural defense mechanism better than 1-min exposures under greenhouse conditions. UV-C nighttime applications had no negative effects on the metabolic activity of plants; it did not affect plant growth, yield quality, or quantity. Initial data suggest that nighttime UV-C treatments have minimal lasting impact on the epiphytic microflora of the plants. In addition, some studies have shown that applying UV-C irradiation reduced the appearance of sour rot disease complex and downy mildew (caused by *Plasmopara viticola*) in some grapevine varieties. Implementation of this type of plant protection can provide additional tools in sustainable grape production, minimizing the use of synthetic fungicides, slowing down the evolution of pathogen resistance, improving human and environmental health. Numerous studies highlight the potential of integrating UV light treatments as an effective and sustainable strategy for managing powdery mildew, enhancing yield, and preserving nutritional quality in sustainable and regenerative agricultural systems. However, the initial integration of UV-C technology requires considerable investment and applications optimization to ensure effectiveness and feasibility.

Keywords: UV-C irradiation, powdery mildew, grapevine, IPM, resistance

LACTOFERRIN IN MASTITIS THERAPY: A PROMISING APPROACH TO OVERCOMING ANTIBACTERIAL RESISTANCE

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Mastitis is a significant challenge for animal health and the dairy industry. It is a complex and common disease of dairy cows caused mainly by bacterial pathogens. Traditionally, antibiotics have been used to prevent and treat mastitis, leading to an increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains. As a result, the efficacy of conventional antibiotics is reduced due to antibiotic overuse. Lactoferrin is a naturally occurring iron-binding glycoprotein found mainly in colostrum, milk and other fluids. This glycoprotein has a broad-spectrum antimicrobial and immunomodulatory properties, and has therefore emerged as a potential alternative to antibiotics in the treatment of mastitis. Bovine lactoferrin has many activities and capabilities such as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal and anti-inflammatory functions. In addition to these properties, lactoferrin supports the function of the immune system and enables tissue repair. The antibacterial activity of lactoferrin is linked to with two different mechanisms: firstly, lactoferrin has the ability to bind iron thereby indirectly acting as a bacteriostatic agent and secondly, lactoferrin is able to destabilize the cell membrane by increasing its permeability, leading to cell death. In addition, lactoferrin acts synergistically with other antibacterial proteins in milk such as immunoglobulin G and lysozyme. This review paper highlights mechanisms by which lactoferrin exerts its activity and its potential role in overcoming antibiotic resistance in the treatment of mastitis in dairy cows.

Key words: lactoferrin, antibiotic resistance, bovine mastitis, mastitis therapy

PRUDENT USE OF ANTIBIOTICS IN DOG REPRODUCTION

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Antibiotics are often necessary in the treatment of reproductive disorders in dogs, such as vulvovaginitis, metritis, pyometra, mastitis, prostatitis, orchitis, and infections caused by *Brucella canis*. However, their unjustified use remains a major problem, as the indiscriminate administration of antibiotics can cause more harm than good. A clear understanding of the canine reproductive microbiome, coupled with an awareness of the potential negative effects of antibiotics, is essential for veterinarians to take a responsible and evidence-based approach. Despite the close relationship between humans and dogs, research on the canine genital microbiome remains limited. The inappropriate use of antibiotics in veterinary practice contributes to the development of antibiotic resistance (AMR) and poses a significant threat to the One Health concept. Accurate diagnosis, identification of the causative pathogen and appropriate treatment duration are key factors for effective treatment of reproductive disorders. Antibiotic therapy should only be initiated when clinically indicated, taking into account the duration of treatment, necessity and potential side effects. This approach can help prevent the rise of antimicrobial resistance, which is already a major global issue. On the other hand, successful treatment depends on the form and course of the present reproductive disorders. Acute conditions require aggressive systemic therapy with appropriate antimicrobial agents. In chronic cases, treatment goals should include addressing predisposing factors in addition to using antimicrobial drugs, selected based on antibiogram and pharmacokinetic data. New, alternative drug treatments, with fewer side effects and improved efficacy, are available. Improvement in the diagnosis and treatment of many reproductive diseases of dogs has allowed medical management of some diseases, which at one time could only be managed surgically.

Key words: AMR, canine, disorder

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Contract no. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117].

ONE HEALTH, ONE CHALLENGE: ANTIBIOTIC USE IN PETS

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The One Health concept emphasizes the connection between human, animal, and environmental health, underlining the importance of studying veterinary prescribing habits. While the use of antimicrobials in food-producing animals is well-documented, there is still limited information regarding antibiotic usage in pets. In our study, we aimed to explore the extent and patterns of veterinary prescriptions for companion animals, paying particular attention to antibacterial treatments. This pilot study involved fourteen community pharmacies located in the Southern region of Hungary, with data collection occurring over a two-year period. All veterinary prescriptions dispensed in these pharmacies were manually reviewed. Information extracted included the prescription and dispensing dates, medication name and quantity, dosage instructions, and the animal species treated. Medications were categorized according to the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system. A total of 4877 veterinary prescriptions, issued by 199 veterinarians, were analyzed. The majority of prescriptions were issued for dogs (3193; 65.5%) and cats (793; 16.3%). Of all medications dispensed, 3886 (79.7%) were human pharmaceutical products, while 991 (20.3%) were veterinary medicines. Most prescriptions (3679; 75.4%) were intended for internal use. Among the dispensed medicinal products, 1,694 (34.7%) were identified as containing at least one antibacterial agent. Ophthalmological preparations (ATC code S01) accounted for 723 items, of which 522 were containing antibiotic, and the combination of dexamethasone with tobramycin being the most frequently dispensed product (295 prescriptions; 6%). Systemic antibacterials (ATC code J01) were totaling 575 prescriptions. Within this group, amoxicillin combined with clavulanic acid was the most commonly dispensed active substance (287 prescriptions; 49.9% of all J01 prescriptions). The results emphasize the extensive use of human medicinal products in veterinary settings and the frequent prescription of antibacterials, particularly broad-spectrum penicillins, which may contribute to the emergence of antimicrobial resistance in both animals and humans.

Key words: one health, antibiotic resistance, veterinary antibiotic consumption

Acknowledgments: ITM_NKFIA_TKP2021-EGA-32

EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY IN HONEY TYPES FROM THE WESTERN BALKANS

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Honey has long been recognized for its antimicrobial properties, attributed to factors such as acidity, osmolality, enzymatically generated hydrogen peroxide, polyphenolic compounds, and, in some cases, bioactive substances like methylglyoxal in manuka honey. These natural properties make honey a promising candidate for use as a therapeutic agent against bacterial infections. This study evaluates the antibacterial activity of nineteen honey samples of various botanical origins, including acacia, linden, heather, rapeseed, sunflower, phacelia, basil, anise, sage, chestnut, hawthorn, lavender, and meadow. These samples were sourced from different regions in the Republic of Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Northern Macedonia. The antibacterial activity was assessed by determining the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) values against six bacterial strains: the gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 8739), *Escherichia coli* (clinical strain), and *Proteus mirabilis* (clinical strain), as well as the gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (clinical strain), and *Enterococcus faecalis* (ATCC 29212). MIC values were determined for each honey sample, and results were analyzed to compare the antibacterial efficacy across different honey types. The results revealed that all honey samples demonstrated antibacterial activity, with significant variations between the honey types. Based on the MIC values, the resistance potency of the bacterial strains followed the order: *Escherichia coli* (clinical strain) > *Escherichia coli* (ATCC) > *Enterococcus faecalis* > *Proteus mirabilis* > *Staphylococcus aureus* > *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The honey samples exhibited stronger inhibitory effects on gram-positive bacteria due to the structural differences in the cell walls of gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria. Gram-positive bacteria lack the outer membrane found in gram-negative bacteria, making it easier for antimicrobial agents in honey to penetrate their cell walls. Among the honey samples, linden honey from Fruška Gora and phacelia honey showed the strongest antibacterial activity. Linden honey exhibited MIC values of 3.12% and 6.25% against *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, respectively, while phacelia honey exhibited MIC values of 6.25% and 3.12%. These findings support the hypothesis that the antibacterial properties of honey are influenced by its botanical origin. Previous studies have also highlighted the potent antimicrobial effects of linden and phacelia honeys, especially against gram-positive bacteria such as *S. aureus*. This study demonstrates that honey possesses significant antibacterial potential and that its activity is influenced by its botanical and geographical origin. These findings reinforce the importance of considering honey's floral source when evaluating its therapeutic applications, highlighting the need for further research into the mechanisms behind honey's antibacterial properties.

Key words: Western Balkans honey; antibacterial activity; botanical origin.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Republic of Serbia (Contract No. 451-03-136/2025-03/200222) and by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research (Contract No. 142-451-3503/2023-02).

PROBIOTIC YEAST *Saccharomyces boulardii* INHIBITORY POTENTIAL ON *Candida glabrata* IN VITRO ADHESION IN A PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT ANTIMYCOTICS

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Following the widespread use of immunosuppressive therapy together with broad-spectrum antifungal therapy, the incidence of mucosal and systemic infections caused by *Candida glabrata* has increased significantly in humans. *C. glabrata* is considered as the second most commonly isolated pathogenic yeast after *Candida albicans*. Due to the increasing resistance of *C. glabrata* to existing drugs, it is very important to search for new strategies that help in the treatment of such fungal infections. An increasing number of potential health benefits are attributed to probiotic treatments. They include various bacterial probiotics, while among yeasts only *Saccharomyces boulardii* (nom. nud.) is extensively used as a probiotic and often marketed as a dietary supplement. The beneficial effect of *S. boulardii* in the case of *C. glabrata* infections has not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, we tested the adhesion of pathogenic yeast *C. glabrata* in a co-culture with probiotic yeast *S. boulardii* to polystyrene surface in the presence of antimycotics, namely fluconazole, itraconazole, and amphotericin B. The method used to assess adhesion was crystal violet staining. The selection of antimycotic concentrations used in the adhesion assay was based on the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) obtained by the preliminarily performed microdilution method according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI), standard M27-A2. The results showed that the lowest concentration of antimycotics which significantly reduced the adhesion of *C. glabrata* in the co-cultures were generally higher than the MICs determined according to the CLSI method. We observed weak activity of azoles against *C. glabrata* strains. On the other hand, exposure to various concentrations of amphotericin B significantly reduced the adhesion of *C. glabrata* strains, both in a single culture and in a co-culture with *S. boulardii*. In conclusion, the results of our study indicate that probiotic yeast have an inhibitory potential on the *C. glabrata* adhesion. It's plausible that *S. boulardii* could effectively replace the action of antimycotics in a certain concentration range and with specific strain types. This would certainly change the approach in treating yeast infections.

Key words: antimycotics, adhesion, *Candida glabrata*, *Saccharomyces boulardii*

Acknowledgments: Zorica Tomičić thanks Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia (project No. 142-451-3493/2023-02).

MIND THE GAP: A DEEP DIVE INTO OFFICIAL PAPERS OF HUNGARIAN ANTIBIOTIC POLICY

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is an emerging public health problem globally. Despite the relatively low amount of antimicrobial use in human health care in Hungary, the quality of antimicrobials used is far too suboptimal, and AMR pattern is also worse than the EU average. In animal health the antimicrobial consumption is one of the highest in EU, though there has been a continuous decrease in antimicrobial sales used among food-producing animals in the past decade. Intersectorial collaboration would be essential in antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) governance under the framework of One Health (OH) concept to combat challenges. In order to map the Hungarian situation a systematic literature review was done to find all the available professional documents (strategies, reviews, guidelines, policy briefs, etc.) in animal and human health care settings that would serve as basis for AMS and tries to tackle AMR, moreover, to reveal the representation of OH concept in the documents. Totally forty-six documents were identified (29 related to human health care, 17 to animal health care), all of them created by top governmental or health care organisations, made after 2017. Beside documents of diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of infectious diseases, the most relevant ones describe the Hungarian situation; understand the problem of AMR; identify deficiencies and barriers; offer solutions, interventions and incentives; furthermore, prioritize AMS actions. Unfortunately, only animal health setting constituted its action plan and accomplished more definite regulatory changes towards prudent antimicrobial use. OH approach definitely appeared in the documents, but still is in infancy, intersectorial cooperation is emphasized but remained only theoretical.

Key words: antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial stewardship, one health concept, document analysis

Acknowledgments: This study was carried out within the framework of the Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance Designing One Health Governance for Antimicrobial Stewardship Interventions (DESIGN project) and supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation Fund (Hungary), grant number: 2019- 2.1.7-ERA-NET.

AFLATOXIN M1 IN DONKEY MILK: A WORLDWIDE REVIEW

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Donkey milk is a highly valuable food product due to its beneficial nutritional properties. It is especially appreciated because of its relatively high similarity to human milk and, compared to cow's milk, the significantly lower risk of allergic reactions after consumption. Despite its many nutritional benefits, the quality and above all, the safety of donkey milk requires careful and thorough examination due to the possible presence of various contaminants. Chemical contaminants, including mycotoxins and particularly aflatoxin M1 (AFM1), which is the most significant in the context of milk, represent a major threat to food safety and human health. The aim of this paper is to present, through a comprehensive analysis of the available literature, the current research related to the pathways through which AFM1 ends up in milk, as well as its presence in donkey milk worldwide. Existing legal frameworks are also covered. So far, very few studies have been conducted on the presence of AFM1 in donkey milk compared to research on this issue in the milk of other animals. Furthermore, most of the studies included a relatively small number of samples. The methods most commonly used for analysis were ELISA, although EIA and HPLC-FLD were also utilized. Research was conducted in Serbia, Greece, Cyprus, Croatia, Italy, China, and Germany. In one study from Serbia, as well as those from China, Italy, Germany, Greece, and Cyprus, the concentrations were below 0.005 µg/kg. However, higher concentrations than this were measured in donkey milk in studies conducted in Serbia (60% of samples), Greece (13.9%), and Italy (1.59%). The levels of AFM1 in milk can vary significantly under the influence of different factors such as geographic location, feeding practices, season, and weather conditions, and may be higher in regions with warm and humid climates. To minimize the level of AFM1 in donkey milk, several strategies can be applied, including good agricultural practices, good manufacturing practices, and regular monitoring. It is assumed that donkey milk will be increasingly consumed in the future, mainly due to the growing number of cases of cow's milk allergies. Therefore, it is undoubtedly important to conduct continuous monitoring of donkey milk in order to ensure and improve its quality, but above all, its safety. The potential presence of AFM1 is certainly a significant safety risk for donkey milk, and there is clearly great potential for further research into this issue.

Key words: aflatoxin M1, donkey milk, food safety, preventive measures

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, grant no. 3535, Project Health Protection and Biodiversity Conservation of Domestic Donkeys in the Special Nature Reserve “Zasavica”—PROTECTDonkey, and by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of Implementation and Funding of Research Work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031. The authors are grateful to Slobodan Simić and Nikola Nilić (Special Nature Reserve “Zasavica”, Serbia) for providing technical support.

WHEN KIDS GET SICK: ANTIBIOTIC USE CHARACTERISTICS

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Children aged 0–19 years account for approximately 20% of Hungary’s total population and this age group is considered frequent antibiotic users. Our research focused on analyzing pediatric antibiotic utilization patterns. The study period covered the years from 2019 to 2023. Our focus was on systemic antibiotics (ATC: J01). Data on redeemed and reimbursed prescriptions for children aged 0–19 years were obtained from the Hungarian National Healthcare Service Center. Antibiotic prescriptions were analyzed based on the associated indications (identified by corresponding ICD codes) across different age subgroups. Results were expressed as prescriptions (Rx) per 1000 children per year. Analysis of national pediatric data showed decreased systemic antibiotic use during the COVID-19 pandemic (it was 558 Rx per 1000 children per year in 2019 which dropped to 328 Rx per 1000 children per year in 2021), followed by a moderate rebound (490 Rx per 1000 children per year in 2023). We observed a consistent dominance of respiratory diseases as 53 – 59 % of pediatric antibiotics prescriptions were for indications: ICD J category. Within the pediatric population children aged 0 to 4 years consistently showed the highest antibiotic use in all study years (minimum 804 Rx per 1000 children per year in 2020; maximum: 1476 Rx per 1000 children per year in 2019). At the active substance level, amoxicillin combined with a beta-lactamase inhibitor (J01CR02) was the most frequently prescribed antibiotic in children throughout the study period, followed by azithromycin (J01FA10), Different cephalosporins (J01D subgroup) alternated in the third position over the years, with agents such as cefuroxime (J01DC02 in 2020), cefprozil (J01DC10 in 2019,2021,2023), or cefixime (J01DD08 in 2022). Overall, a significant decline in antibiotic use among children was observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a near return to pre-pandemic levels. Our findings highlight that respiratory tract infections remained the leading indication for antibiotic prescriptions in children in Hungary. Children aged 0–4 years consistently accounted for the highest pediatric antibiotics use. There was a shift toward more broad spectra antibiotic use.

Keywords: Antibiotic consumption trends, Hungary, respiratory infections

Acknowledgement: ITM NKFIA TKP2021-EGA-32

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF RAPESEED HONEY ENRICHED WITH LYOPHILIZED FRUITS

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Honey is a natural product valued for its nutritional, therapeutic, and functional properties, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and wound-healing effects. Its composition varies depending on botanical and geographical origin, which significantly influences its biological activity. Among its bioactivities, antibacterial potential is one of the most widely studied and clinically relevant. The antibacterial effects of honey arise from a combination of physical and chemical factors. These include low water activity, high sugar content creating osmotic pressure, low pH that creates an unfavourable environment for microbial growth, and the enzymatic generation of hydrogen peroxide. In addition, honey contains a variety of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and other secondary metabolites that exert direct antimicrobial action, either by disrupting bacterial cell membranes, interfering with DNA replication, or inhibiting key metabolic enzymes. This study evaluated the antibacterial activity of rapeseed honey samples enriched with various types of lyophilized fruits, aiming to enhance the honey's functionality. A total of eight samples were analyzed: seven honey-based products enriched with 10% of different fruits (sour cherry, strawberry, blueberry, raspberry, blackberry, orange, and pineapple) and a control sample of rapeseed honey. The samples were obtained from a local beekeeping farm in the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Serbia, and stored at room temperature in the dark until analysis. Antibacterial activity was determined using the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) method against six bacterial strains: *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 8739 and ATCC 10536), *Enterococcus faecalis* (ATCC 29212), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 25923), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (ATCC 12228), and *Proteus hauseri* (ATCC 13315). The results showed that rapeseed honey exhibited limited antibacterial activity, with MIC values higher than 25% for all tested strains. In contrast, all honey-based products demonstrated enhanced antibacterial effects, particularly against Gram-positive bacteria. The lowest MIC values were recorded in samples enriched with raspberry, blueberry, and sour cherry, especially against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The pineapple-enriched sample also exhibited activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 12.5%. Honey-based products likely act through multiple mechanisms, including disruption of bacterial cell walls, inhibition of essential enzymes, and interference with microbial quorum sensing. Significant negative correlations were observed between total phenolic content (TPC) and MIC values for Gram-positive strains, indicating the important role of polyphenols from fruit lyophilizates in antibacterial activity. A similar trend was observed for total flavonoid content (TFC), particularly against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The most effective samples were those enriched with berries, likely due to the presence of bioactive compounds such as quercetin, kaempferol, and anthocyanins. These findings highlight the potential of enriching honey with lyophilized fruits as an effective approach to enhance its antimicrobial properties. Such functional products may be useful in preventing and treating mild bacterial infections and could be applied as natural antimicrobial agents in the food and pharmaceutical industries.

Key words: rapeseed honey; fruit lyophilizates; antibacterial activity

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Republic of Serbia (Contract No. 451-03-136/2025-03/200222) and by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research (Contract No. 142-451-3503/2023-02).

AGING AND QUALITY OF ANTIBIOTIC USE?

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In Hungary, a significant portion of the population is elderly, with one in five people aged 65 or older. The aim of this study was to examine the trends in antibiotic use among the elderly in the Hungarian ambulatory care sector between 2019 and 2023. National-level utilization data on redeemed and reimbursed prescriptions for the elderly were retrieved from the Hungarian National Health Insurance Fund Administration (NEAK) statistics. Our analysis focused on systemic antibiotics (ATC code: J01). The data were categorized by gender, specific age groups and indications (identified by corresponding ICD codes). Additionally, antibiotic use was analyzed according to ATC subgroups and the WHO's 2023 AWaRe classification. Results were presented as the number of prescriptions (Rx) per 1,000 inhabitants annually. In 2019, the prescription rate of systemic antibiotics (ATC: J01) among elderly was 627 Rx per 1000 inhabitants per year. A slight decline was noted in the subsequent years, with 523 Rx per 1,000 inhabitants in 2020 and 521 Rx per 1000 inhabitants in 2021, both years being impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. However, in 2022, there was a noticeable increase in the number of prescriptions, exceeding the pre-pandemic levels (641 Rx per 1000 inhabitants per year). Based on the WHO AWaRe classification, we observed a decrease in the use of Watch antibiotics during the COVID-19 pandemic from 373 to 300 Rx per 1000 inhabitants per year (a 20% decrease). However, after pandemic, their use exceeded the previous levels (390 Rx/ 1000 inhabitants/ year). Regarding the percental share of Access group antibiotics (Access %) of the total systemic antibiotic use (J01), we observed a rate of ~40% in all study years. Gender-related differences were observed across age subgroups. In 2023, women aged 65–70 had a ~20 % higher rate of antibiotic utilization compared to men in all years. We detected that the majority of antibacterial prescriptions among the elderly were for RTIs (ICD: J) and UTIs (ICD: N), accounting for approximately 40% and 20% of total antibiotic use. Co-amoxiclav consistently led the top list of antibiotics, accounting for about 20% of prescriptions. In the ranking some changes were detected: both ciprofloxacin and levofloxacin dropped from second place, while azithromycin became the second most commonly used antibacterial agent. Antibiotic utilization among the elderly showed an initial decline during pandemic years, but subsequently exceeded the previous levels. Watch antibiotic use declined during the pandemic but rebounded afterward; the proportion of Access use stayed stable and suboptimal. Respiratory and urinary tract infections consistently remained the primary indications for systemic antibiotic prescriptions. Although a declining trend was observed in the use of fluoroquinolones during the study period, their overall prescription rate remained considerable among the elderly population.

Key words: AWaRe classification, COVID-19, Hungary

Acknowledgement: ITM_NKFIA_TKP2021-EGA-32

BIOLOGICAL CONTROL OF *MACROPHOMINA PHASEOLINA* IN SUGAR BEET: AN ALTERNATIVE TO FUNGICIDES IN THE CONTEXT OF ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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Biological control of plant pathogens offers a sustainable alternative to chemical treatments by harnessing beneficial microorganisms to suppress disease. This approach is gaining importance as agriculture practice shifts to more environmentally friendly practices. The charcoal root rot is an emerging disease of sugar beet that significantly reduces yield and affects the economic viability of production. The fungicide treatment in the control of charcoal root rot is not effective, environmentally and economically justified measure. On the other hand, fungicides can disrupt the balance of beneficial microorganisms in the soil and that their inadequate and excessive use leads to the development of pathogen resistance to fungicides. Biological agents such as *Trichoderma* spp. can replace fungicides application to some extent and play an important role in maintaining plant health in "eco-friendly" agricultural systems. The objectives of this research were to determine the antagonist activity of selected *Trichoderma harzianum* isolates on two *Macrophomina phaseolina* isolates *in vivo*. A significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was observed between treatments, showing that application of *T. harzianum* isolates T2 and T12, either alone or in combination, significantly reduced DSI (disease severity index) compared to the control. On the other hand, commercial biopesticides and one synthetic fungicide did not express a satisfactory effect on the control of *M. phaseolina*, where DSI was at the same level of statistical significance as the control in the case of both tested *M. phaseolina* isolates. These findings highlight the potential of *Trichoderma harzianum* as an effective and environmentally sustainable alternative to synthetic fungicides in managing *Macrophomina phaseolina*-induced charcoal root rot in sugar beet, contributing to the reduction of fungicide use and the risk of antimicrobial resistance development in agroecosystems.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Trichoderma harzianum*

CONTROL OF ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF ANTIBIOTICS ON THE MARKET OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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Monitoring the antimicrobial activity of antibiotics available on the market is essential for ensuring drug quality and efficacy. For active ingredients unsuitable for determination by instrumental methods, we apply microbiological assay techniques in accordance with Ph. Eur. 2.7.2. Two methods are used: the diffusion method, based on measuring zones of microbial growth inhibition on solid media, and the turbidimetric method, which assesses microbial growth inhibition in liquid media by measuring turbidity. These methods are applied to both single-ingredient and combination medicinal products, where active substances are often being analyzed exclusively by microbiological methods. In other cases, a combined approach, including microbiological and instrumental techniques, such as HPLC, is used. Between 2019 and 2024, a total of 71 microbiological assays of antibiotics from the Bosnia and Herzegovina market were performed. Of these, 41 samples were injection solutions, powders for reconstitution, sprays or eye drops, 9 ointments, 8 creams, 6 vaginal tablets, and 7 solid oral forms such as tablets and capsules. Before laboratory testing begins, the manufacturer's documentation is reviewed to ensure full compliance with relevant regulations, especially Ph. Eur. requirements. Testing is delayed until documentation is confirmed compliant. In 17 cases, testing was postponed due to non-compliant documentation, while other issues involved necessary adjustments to assay methods. This review stage is considered a clock stop, pausing the testing until all issues are resolved and corrected documentation is submitted. Laboratory analysis proceeds only after compliance is confirmed. All tested samples met the specified criteria for antimicrobial activity, with no observed cases of reduced potency. As a result of the complex nature of certain dosage form matrices, particularly semi-solid and topical preparations, 6 % of samples required repeated testing. The primary cause of these repetitions was the challenge of achieving reliable quantitative extraction of antibiotics from complex dosage matrices. In less frequent cases, repeated testing was required due to procedural issues unrelated to the antibiotic's quality, such as inadequate storage of reference standards or sample preparation. Diffusion assays were used in 93% (66 out of 71) of the tested samples, while turbidimetric methods were applied less frequently. The most frequently tested active substances were: neomycin, lysozyme, vancomycin, gentamicin, nystatin, polymyxin B, and oxytetracycline. Antibiotics are regularly controlled to ensure that only tested and potent medicines are present on the market. By verifying their antimicrobial activity, we help ensure that these medicines achieve the intended therapeutic effect when used according to recommended dosage regimens. This control plays a key role in the fight against antimicrobial resistance and highlights the importance of regulatory oversight in public health protection.

Keywords: quality control, microbiological assay, antimicrobial activity, Ph. Eur. 2.7.2

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE OF *ESCHERICHIA COLI* ISOLATED FROM ONE DAY OLD BROILERS

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The irrational use of antibiotics has caused numerous global issues in both human and veterinary medicine. In intensive poultry production, antimicrobial agents are extensively used not only for treating and controlling diseases but also for preventive purposes. These practices have significantly contributed to the high prevalence of *Escherichia coli* resistance to certain antibiotic classes. The emergence of antimicrobial resistance results in substantial losses in poultry production and poses a potential risk to human health. The aim of this study was to present data on the antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* isolates, isolated from one day old broiler chickens that died during transport to the farm. The research included samples collected from farms in the Srem and Južnobački districts during 2023 and 2024. A classical bacteriological technique was used to isolate *E. coli*. Determination of resistance level for pathogenic bacteria is performed in National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial Resistance (NRL-AMR) in veterinary medicine in Serbia. The degree of resistance was tested using the disk diffusion method according to the document of CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute). Our research contained 12 different antibiotics (amoxicillin, ampicillin, enrofloxacin, flumequine, erythromycin, gentamicin, neomycin, streptomycin, tetracycline, doxycycline, florfenicol and trimethoprim-sulfomet). In 2023, a total of 37 samples were received, of which 32 (86.48%) were positive for *E. coli*. In 2024, a total of 32 samples were analyzed, of which 23 were positive for *E. coli* (71,87%). The lowest rate of resistance was observed during both analyzed years against florfenicol, while the highest percentage of resistance was recorded against erythromycin. The other two of most common antibiotics in 2023 were flumequine (48,65%) and ampicillin (43,24%), while for 2024 were flumequine (78,26%) and amoxicillin (73,91%). Our results showed different levels of resistance of *E. coli* isolated from day-old broilers to antibiotics which is a worrying factor. The continued irresponsible and irrational use of antibiotics on farms contributes to the spread of pathogenic microorganisms, resistant to multiple antibiotic classes. The problem with increased resistance is a significant challenge in disease control and it underscores the urgent need for effective antibiotic stewardship in poultry farming.

Key words: AMR, *E.coli*, disk diffusion, broiler

Acknowledgments: This study was funded by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia by the Contract of implementation and funding of research work of NIV-NS in 2025, Contract No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200031.

ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS PSEUDINTERMEDIUS* ISOLATES FROM CANINE BACTERIAL SKIN INFECTIONS IN HUNGARY

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the greatest challenges of our time. Ensuring the sustainability of antibiotics is a global priority, as the development of new antimicrobial agents is slow and expensive and cannot keep pace with the rapid emergence and spread of AMR. Prudent antibiotic use is therefore essential. Bacterial dermatitis is the second most frequently diagnosed condition in dogs in veterinary practice, making it one of the key indications for antibacterial treatment in companion animal medicine. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of 22 antibiotics commonly used to treat bacterial skin infections in dogs. Using the microdilution method, we tested 82 clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*, including 3 methicillin-resistant isolates (MRSP). All 82 isolates were sensitive to rifampicin and vancomycin (100%). High sensitivity rates were observed for oxacillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftiofur, amikacin, and florfenicol (>95%). Cephalexin (86.6%), enrofloxacin (84.1%), gentamicin (81.7%), potassium sulfonamide (80.6%), and ceftazidime (75.6%) also showed strong efficacy. Moderate sensitivity was recorded for clindamycin (65.9%), marbofloxacin (67.1%), azithromycin (61%), oxytetracycline (54.9%), and doxycycline (54.9%). Sensitivity to penicillin (37.8%) and amoxicillin (22.2%) was low. Among the three MRSP isolates, susceptibility was retained only for amikacin, rifampicin, florfenicol, vancomycin, and in one case - gentamicin. Alarmingly, only enrofloxacin showed limited efficacy among AMEG category B fluoroquinolones. The results suggest that amoxicillin-clavulanic acid and cephalexin remain viable first-line therapies for skin infections caused by *S. pseudintermedius* in dogs. However, the emergence of resistance, particularly to fluoroquinolones, is concerning. For MRSP infections, amikacin and rifampicin should be prioritized. To support sustainable antibiotic use and minimize the spread of AMR, it is essential to perform susceptibility testing prior to treatment to ensure appropriate antibiotic selection.

Key words: AMR, dermatitis, *Staphylococcus pseudintermedius*, MRSP, sensitivity testing

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by Project no. RRF-2.3.1-21-2022-00001, implemented with the support provided by the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), financed under the National Recovery Fund budget estimate, RRF-2.3.1-21 funding scheme.

3D PRINTING: ROLE IN COMBATING ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

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Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents one of the biggest issues today, and it is believed that this number will increase dramatically in the next 25 years. To combat AMR, scientists are exploring modern solutions, including 3D printing. This technology builds solid objects by layering material one layer at a time using computer-aided design (CAD). This study investigates how 3D printing can be used to fight AMR, including developing innovative antibiotic delivery systems, implants, medical devices, and human tissue models for assessing treatment efficacy and testing bacterial interactions. Using the keywords “antimicrobial resistance,” “3D printing,” and “3D printing antibiotics”, data was gathered from the PubMed database. The methodology involved review of scientific literature through these keyword searches. The role of 3D printing can be divided into several segments: testing the antibiotic resistance, simulation of the AMR, and AMR risk reduction and control. In the first segment, 3D printing is being used in developing portable devices for diagnostics, sensor inserts, and microfluidic chips. These developments offer rapid diagnostics of AMR, on-site testing, and efficient drug delivery. Regarding the simulation of AMR, 3D printing provides the ability to produce complex, native-like bacterial communities. Methods include bacteria-loaded gels, photosensitive materials, bacteria-based printing, and microarrays. Although they have great potential, their application is still limited in antibiotic response and AMR emergence. The third segment, risk reduction and control, includes 3D-printed targeted drug delivery systems, thereby reducing systemic and microbiome exposure. 3D-printed materials can be produced for controlled drug release, combination therapy, and even inherent antimicrobial activity. While 3D printing technology is very promising, some of its limitations include the cost of clinical trials and possible issues like cell toxicity and necrosis, biocompatibility, and long-term effects on health.

Key words: 3D printing, antimicrobial resistance, 3D printing antibiotics

Acknowledgments: This research is supported by the project funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (451-03-136/2025-03/200114).

UNCOVERING THE CULPRIT: *NEOPESTALOTIOPSIS* SPP. AS AN AGGRESSIVE THREAT TO BLUEBERRY CROPS IN SERBIA

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Blueberry (*Vaccinium corymbosum* L. family Ericaceae) production in Serbia is of significant economic value. Its cultivation is steadily increasing due to flavor and health benefits of the fruits, but also high product marketability and high rate of investment returns. Depending on the region, blueberries are cultivated either in open fields or in containers. Whichever cultural practice is used, blueberries may exhibit symptoms of dieback, stem and twig blight especially on seedlings. The objective of this study was to identify the pathogen responsible for these symptoms and assess its pathogenicity on blueberry seedlings. For this purpose, a comprehensive analysis was conducted using both morphological and molecular diagnostic tools. Fungal isolation was performed from the tissue of necrotic shoot using standard phytopathological procedures. Based on morphological characteristics, four isolates were initially classified into the genus *Neopestalotiopsis*. To confirm this, molecular identification was conducted using two genetic markers: Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region and β -tubulin gene. Sequence analysis via BLAST and phylogenetic analysis confirmed that all isolates clustered within the genus *Neopestalotiopsis*. Pathogenicity tests were carried out on healthy, potted blueberry plants of the 'Duke' cultivar, a commonly grown variety in Serbia, under controlled greenhouse conditions (daily temperature of approximately 25°C during the day/15°C at night, controlled photoperiod of 16/8 hours [day/night], and regular watering to avoid drought stress). Five mm diameter mycelial plugs were taken from 7-day-old cultures grown on PDA and placed on wounded tissue with the mycelium in contact with the exposed cambium. For the negative control, plugs of non inoculated PDA were used. After 17 days, all isolates induced symptoms resembling those observed in the field. This study proved that *Neopestalotiopsis* spp. is a pathogen causing dieback, stem and twig blight in Serbian blueberry orchards. Further research on this topic is necessary in order to pinpoint the specific species involved, understand their epidemiology, and examine the environmental factors favoring disease development. As blueberry cultivation continues to grow in Serbia, early detection, proper diagnostic techniques, and the production of healthy cuttings are crucial for minimizing the impact of this pathogen. The results of this study contribute to a broader understanding of pestalotioid fungi in berry crops and offer valuable insights for developing sustainable practices to ensure the health and productivity of blueberry plants in Serbia.

Keywords: *Neopestalotiopsis* spp., blueberry, dieback and twig blight

MONITORING AND REGULATORY CONTROL OF ANTIBIOTIC RESIDUES IN MILK: CURRENT CHALLENGES AND ANALYTICAL APPROACHES WITH A ONE HEALTH PERSPECTIVE

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Monitoring antibiotic residues in milk is essential for public health protection and combating antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Within the One Health framework - which emphasizes the interconnected health of humans, animals, and the environment - ensuring milk safety has become a global priority. Residues in milk can cause allergic reactions, disrupt the human microbiota, and contribute to AMR, particularly in vulnerable populations such as children and immunocompromised individuals. International regulatory agencies, including the Codex Alimentarius, European Union (EU), and U.S. FDA, have established Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs) to control antibiotic presence in food. EU Regulation 2019/6 also requires specific withdrawal periods after treatment to ensure that milk entering the food chain complies with safety standards. Nonetheless, trace residues may still occur. The problem is more pronounced in low- and middle-income countries, where weak regulations, lack of diagnostic tools, and limited awareness of responsible antibiotic use contribute to higher levels of residues in milk. In countries such as Serbia and across the Western Balkans, the ongoing challenges in regulating veterinary antibiotic use highlight the need for stronger intersectoral collaboration to prevent residue contamination and reduce AMR risks. This situation calls for a coordinated One Health approach involving veterinarians, public health professionals, and regulatory authorities. Residue detection combines screening and confirmatory methods. While rapid assays such as microbiological tests, ELISA, and biosensors offer cost-effective screening, confirmatory methods like LC-MS/MS and HPLC provide high accuracy but are expensive and environmentally demanding. Processed dairy products present additional challenges, as heat treatments reduce but do not fully eliminate residues. More research is needed to develop reliable detection methods for these products. In conclusion, a comprehensive One Health strategy is vital for minimizing antibiotic residues in milk, reducing AMR risks, and ensuring food safety on a global scale.

Keywords: antibiotic residues, antimicrobial resistance, milk safety, One Health, Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs), veterinary antibiotics, residue monitoring

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Contract no. 451-03-137/2025-03/200117].

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Broj i datum dozvole leka: 323-01-00380-19-001 od 19.03.2020.
Datum poslednje revizije Sažetka Karakteristika leka: Decembar,
2020. godine.

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

619:616:636(082)

**INTERNATIONAL Conference Antimicrobial Resistance -
Current State and Perspectives (4 ; 2025 ; Novi Sad)**

Book of abstracts / 4th International Conference
Antimicrobial Resistance - Current State and Perspectives,
19-21 June 2025., Novi Sad, Serbia ; [editor in chief Zorana
Kovačević]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Agriculture, 2025 (Novi
Sad : Constanta). - 90 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 500.

ISBN 978-86-7520-634-7

a) Ветеринарска медицина -- Зборници

COBISS.SR-ID 170860553